

D6.5

Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Report (M39)

AUSTRALO

D6.5

Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Final Report (M39)

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Abstract

This deliverable presents DATAMITE’s impact assessment and combines the work and the outcomes of the exploitation and standardisation task activities. It describes the development of outcomes to the Exploitable Results and how consortium partners intend to utilise them after the end of the project, as well as the valuable lessons learned from use cases. All outcomes from exploitation workshops, pilot validations, and go-to-market activities up to M39 are included in this report, which builds on the D6.4 report (M18).

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Impact, Exploitation, Standardisation, Business Cases, Business Model, Strategy, Data Monetisation, Exploitation Pathways, Intellectual Property Value Proposition, Open Source

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to the DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoD	AI on Demand
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CCMC	CEN-CENELEC Management Centre
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DGM	Data Governance Module
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DMMM	Data Monetisation Maturity Model
DQV	Data Quality Vocabulary
DSM	Data Sharing Module
DSEM	Data Security Module
DSTM	Data Sharing and Trading Module
DQM	Data Quality Module
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector
ECL	Eclipse Foundation Europe GmbH
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPL	Eclipse Public License
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IP	Intellectual Property
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JTC	Joint Technical Committee
KER	Key Exploitable
M	Month (project milestone)
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology License
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UDRG	User Defined Rules Generator
WI	Work Item
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

At the end of the DATAMITE project, we can highlight the results turned into exploitable results contributing to the EU competitiveness on Data Monetisation: the open-source framework, its modules and components, was tested in six industrial pilots across agriculture, energy, telecommunications, and meteorology, where the Pilots saw improvements in data quality, governance, security, and sharing. While adoption in large organisations often gets complicated by local systems, internal rules, and capacity constraints—such as a utility facing long procurement cycles compared to a smaller firm that can adapt quickly but lacks the necessary funding— DATAMITE assets come to play an important role, from tools to strategies and training materials, that can help them make the best of their data. Below, the portfolio of five key assets is outlined:

Architecture Reference Implementation: This is the open-source release that acts as a starting point for organisations that want to adopt DATAMITE assets by laying out the architecture, its APIs, and what the framework does, so teams can efficiently strategise their tasks around data with reduced complexities and unknowns. It's the De facto standard for future developments, significantly expanding the project's reach.

Open-Source Core Framework: The core framework with its main modules in one place, so governance, quality, security, and sharing and trading. The Framework contains the DSM, DQM, DGM, DSEM, and DSTM modules, which work as a set, while most organisations can still implement them in stages based on their needs.

Business Model Strategies: This asset is connecting the technical work to commercial reality. It offers guidance and training material on data monetisation, with strategy options, business model templates, and a way to think through what might be sold, to whom, and on what terms. It will help organisations improve their understanding, prepare and monetise their datasets.

Data Support Tools: These are the extra components – the data harmonisation, data anonymisation, fairness & data bias, data ingestion & storage, and data discovery tools – can be used as an extension to the core framework. They are shaped by end-user needs, which can be very specific, and can be deployed on their own or integrated into the organisation's systems.

Business & Technical Training: Consortium partners are tech experts who can provide consulting services and materials related to implementation, adaptation, and compliance, as well as ongoing technical support to organisations, parallel to training, which is an important part of the EU upskilling strategy, because tooling without skills is a short-lived win.

Overall, the five assets make DATAMITE appear ready to extend beyond the project by aligning with the organisation's data handling challenges with common issues faced daily, such as data trapped in silos, systems that do not communicate, skills shortages, and the ongoing pressure of compliance work under GDPR and newer regulations.

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable Purpose and Scope

This **D6.5 – Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Report (M39)**, builds on **D6.1 – Impact Master Plan (M6)** and **D6.4 – Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Interim Report (M18)**. It sets out the exploitation plan for each partner and each KER, based on the progress till M39. The continuity and further development of the exploitation followed the first analysis of the market, the challenges, the DATAMITE positioning and value and included the feedback from the implementation in three use cases and six pilots. The DATAMITE’s strategic vision is to support adoption across sectors and organisation types (SMEs, large enterprises, public administrations); while addressing constraints they currently face related to data handling. The exploitation strategies and the sustainability plans are covering post-project, the DATAMITE Open Alliance, partner commitments, and replication opportunities as identified to date. Each key exploitable result contains info about its value proposition, commercialisation approach, business model, and feedback gathered from use cases/early adopters, through workshops and meetings.

1.2. Document Structure

The deliverable is organised as follows. It mirrors the objectives set out above.

- **Executive Summary**
- **Section 1 - Introduction**
- **Section 2 - DATAMITE Portfolio of Solutions**
- **Section 3 - DATAMITE’s Exploitation Pathways & Sustainability**
- **Section 4 - Standardisation**
- **Conclusions**

1.3. DATAMITE Strategic Vision

DATAMITE’s strategic vision is to support European organisations—large enterprises and SMEs—in making better use of their data assets and, where appropriate, turning them into revenue. The project does this through a modular, open-source, multi-domain framework aimed at data monetisation, interoperability, and data exchange and trading. Over time, the work moved

from core technical build-up to pre-commercial deployment (targeting a Technology Readiness Level of 7).

At an internal level, DATAMITE is intended to provide users with tools to support data quality work and the day-to-day adherence to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. The open access training (reports, documents, tutorials, workshops) material is part of that, because skills are often the blocker, not the software.

At an external level, the framework is built so organisations can keep control of their data while still exploring new ways of handling it, including revenue paths from sharing or trading and interoperating with broader data infrastructures, including the International Data Spaces (IDS), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), and other data spaces and markets. The architecture also supports DIH sandboxing, which could help onboard low-tech SMEs into the European data economy.

For growth and market entry, information gathered by implementing the DATAMITE solutions in the pilots in the three use cases was very valuable as a start for the initial deployments, which can help small clusters of adoption, and later connect them into something larger. The plan I described is in three phases:

- **Phase 1 – Enhance and Update (2026):** Keep improving what was validated in the pilots, and push robustness further. The intention is to move TRL levels from 6-7 to 7-8 and to assess in real environments how the solutions behave under different implementation conditions and in different sectors.
- **Phase 2 – Expand and Replicate (2027-2028):** Broaden the adoption, adding new features and maintaining the code, which comes from early adopter feedback and market needs, then replicate implementations across partner networks and similar organisations, where it is feasible and still makes sense.
- **Phase 3 – Converge and Integrate (2029-2030):** As the validated solutions evolve, a more unified DATAMITE open-source product ecosystem could emerge. It should be able to serve more sectors and more organisation types.

2. DATAMITE Portfolio of Solutions

The DATAMITE Portfolio of Solutions groups the main components developed and validated during the project. They are meant to cover technical needs and business needs around data monetisation, but the adoption effort will not be the same everywhere. Some organisations can utilise the open-source framework; others can consult the monetisation strategies; and the consulting material will remain valid for all interested parties.

2.1. Architecture Reference Implementation

The DATAMITE Architecture Reference Implementation serves as an open-source blueprint for organisations seeking to deploy the framework in their own environments. It is built for developers, system integrators, and IT architects who need a reference for integrating with legacy corporate databases (e.g., PostgreSQL, MongoDB, MariaDB), and it can support DIHs that run sandbox environments for SMEs. It includes architecture specs, API documentation for module interfaces, integration patterns and deployment set-ups for common scenarios, and sample implementations that reflect typical use cases.

2.2. Open-Source Core Framework

The core software Framework is an open-source set of modules that supports the data provider lifecycle. It covers governance, quality, sharing, and security. The open-source model matters here because it gives organisations room to adapt components, avoid lock-in, and see what is going on under the hood. The module set—Data Governance Module (DGM), Data Quality Module (DQM), Data Security Module (DSEM), Data Sharing Module (DSM), and Data Sharing and Trading Module (DSTM)—can be deployed on its own or combined, based on the organisation's needs. The aim is to align with European regulatory and ethical requirements for data management.

Figure 1. DATAMITE Framework

Data Governance Module (DGM)

The Data Governance Module helps organisations manage their data assets by including features such as discovery, classification, access control, and compliance management. A key feature is a central metadata repository that supports DCAT-compliant data cataloguing, simplifying data organisation and discovery. The module also offers comprehensive data lineage tracking, allowing organisations to trace data from its origin through various transformations and uses while consistency is maintained through glossary management, ensuring uniform terminology across the organisation. Additionally, it provides detailed access control and permission settings to restrict sensitive data access to authorised personnel and includes compliance monitoring tools ensuring adherence to GDPR, the Data Act, and other sector-specific regulations. Finally, it integrates data quality metrics and reporting to support ongoing quality assurance and transparency, directly linking governance activities to data quality improvement.

Data Quality Module (DQM)

The Data Quality Module improves the evaluation, monitoring, and enhancement of data quality across various dimensions by ensuring that the data assets satisfy requirements for internal applications, AI/ML initiatives, and potential external monetisation. The module offers a broad range of features to maintain high data standards, assessing factors such as accuracy, completeness, consistency, and timeliness, while automated profiling and anomaly detection enable organisations to quickly identify and resolve issues. Users can customise quality rules and

validation logic to meet specific needs, with user-friendly dashboards for scoring and reporting that simplify progress tracking and showcasing improvements. By integrating with data governance workflows, the module manages quality-related metadata effectively and aligns with ISO/IEC 5259 standards, making it suitable for AI use cases and ensuring future readiness of data quality management.

Data Security Module (DSEM)

The Data Security Module supports secure and controlled data sharing. It is intended to maintain data sovereignty while supporting privacy compliance through security mechanisms and usage-control approaches. The module offers a comprehensive suite of security and control features to ensure robust data protection and trustworthy exchange. Organisations benefit from data sovereignty and usage control mechanisms built on IDS principles, enabling them to retain control over how their data is used and shared, while fine-grained access control and attribute-based policies allow for tailored permissions, ensuring only authorised individuals have access to sensitive information. Secure data exchange connectors facilitate safe transfer between systems, while encryption and anonymisation services add an extra layer of privacy protection. Audit logging and compliance tracking provide transparency and support adherence to regulatory requirements. Integration with identity management systems ensures seamless authentication and user management, tying security measures directly to organisational processes and making the module suitable for environments where privacy and compliance are paramount.

Data Sharing Module (DSM)

The Data Sharing Module supports publication and discovery of data assets across data spaces, marketplaces, and collaborative platforms. The intent is to help organisations participate in data-sharing arrangements within the European data economy.

The Data Sharing Module provides a full range of features to assist organisations operating within the European data economy. It supports multi-platform data publishing across systems like GAIA-X, IDS, AloD, Zenodo, and various commercial marketplaces. Organisations can clearly package and describe their data products to promote wider access and understanding. The module includes discovery and search capabilities, helping users locate relevant data assets within data spaces and marketplaces. It also offers negotiation and contracting tools to make data sharing agreements more straightforward. Integration with governance and security modules ensures that all activities remain compliant and protected. Moreover, the use of standards-based metadata

and semantic interoperability enhances consistency and compatibility across platforms, making collaborative data sharing more efficient and dependable.

Data Support Tools Module (DSTM)

The Data Support Tools Module provides business-oriented tools and frameworks to support data monetisation. This includes pricing approaches, valuation methods, and business model templates.

The module provides a wide range of features to help organisations monetise their data assets. These include strong frameworks for data valuation and practical pricing models, offering a base for determining the financial value of data. Business model canvas templates support the development and commercialisation of data products, while cost-benefit analysis tools help evaluate the potential returns of various monetisation strategies. Organisations also gain from revenue tracking and analytics capabilities, enabling continuous performance monitoring. Seamless integration with data sharing and security modules ensures all activities are secure and compliant. Additionally, compliance checking tools assist organisations in meeting regulatory requirements for data trading, giving reassurance when navigating legal standards within the European data economy.

2.3. Business (Monetisation) Strategies

This component provides frameworks and guidance to help organisations organise their data monetisation work. It supports the search for revenue streams, the basics of data valuation, and the choice of pricing approaches for data products. The material also covers different exploitation routes, including direct commercial data provision, technology development, and internal optimisation, because not every organisation can—or should—take the same route.

Key Capabilities:

- **Data Valuation and Pricing Setup:** Guidelines to help organisations assess the financial worth of their data assets and implement practical pricing structures for external trading or licensing.
- **Revenue Stream Identification:** Methodologies to pinpoint new monetisation opportunities, whether through direct commercial data sales, subscription models, or developing new data-driven services.
- **Strategic Ecosystem Integration:** Frameworks for positioning and publishing data products within established European data spaces and marketplaces, such as Gaia-X,

Pontus-X, the International Data Spaces (IDS), and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

- **Exploitation Route Selection:** Decision-making support to help companies choose the most viable path for their data assets by the selection of direct commercial exploitation (paid provision to end users), technological exploitation (building products on top of the data), or internal research and optimisation.
- **Regulatory and Compliance Alignment:** Strategic mapping to ensure business models comply with European legal frameworks, specifically the GDPR, the Data Act, and the Data Governance Act. This capability reduces the legal and operational risks associated with data sharing and intermediary services.

2.4. Advanced Components (Support Tools)

DATAMITE includes cross-cutting tools that extend the core framework, mostly to address sectoral needs and practical constraints that arise when running the system. The demonstrators validated a set of these tools, and the capabilities below reflect that work. The User Defined Rules Generator (UDRG) enables businesses to implement bespoke quality checks and business logic, ensuring their data consistently meets both internal and external standards. To protect privacy and comply with GDPR, sensitive information can be securely anonymised before any dataset is shared or traded. The Data Product Composition Tool streamlines the packaging of raw datasets, metadata, access policies, and glossaries into structured, monetisable data products, enhancing the commercial potential of data assets. Integrated solutions like Trino and data harmonisation modules facilitate seamless querying and unification of information across a range of databases—including PostgreSQL, MongoDB, and MariaDB—without the need to physically transfer data. For organisations looking to broaden their reach, data assets can be directly published to established European networks such as Gaia-X, Pontus-X, and the EU AI-on-Demand platform, using specialised brokers and Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) extensions. Finally, robust transaction logging tools ensure all data-sharing activities are transparently tracked and audited, enabling organisations to maintain accountability and trust in their data operations.

2.5. Tech Experts & Training Services

Skills gaps still slow participation in the European data economy, even when the tooling is in place. DATAMITE addresses this with consulting and training resources, including open-source material for technical and business audiences. The content covers how to implement the

DATAMITE framework, how to apply FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles, and the business basics needed when data is treated as a strategic asset and, in some cases, traded. Training resources are designed to guide users through the installation, configuration, and operation of the framework, ensuring practical understanding at every stage. The users can learn the fundamentals of data governance and how to apply FAIR principles, equipping them to manage information responsibly and efficiently. The data valuation techniques and pricing strategies are covered too, helping organisations unlock the commercial value of their data products. Compliance is a central focus, with clear guidance on meeting requirements under the GDPR, the Data Act, and the Data Governance Act so that teams can navigate the regulatory landscape. Hands-on support is provided for using tools like the User Defined Rules Generator, Data Product Composition Tool, and for integrating across platforms, making technical adoption seamless. Commercialisation strategies are woven throughout, blending technical know-how with business execution to maximise returns. Above all, these resources directly address the skills gap in the European data economy, offering tailored development for both IT teams and management so everyone can participate confidently and effectively.

Figure 2. DATAMITE's MooC Platform

3. DATAMITE's Exploitation Pathways & Sustainability

DATAMITE defines five exploitation pathways intended to carry the work beyond March 2026. They were first outlined in **D6.4** and then adjusted after M39 pilot validation and the market-facing steps taken late in the project. What happens next is harder to pin down. Uptake will depend on conditions outside this deliverable.

Pathway	DATAMITE Final Status
Research	Conference & Journal publications; follow-on Horizon Europe proposals in preparation, National & International funding Schemes
Monetisation	Commercial services model finalised; consulting/training offering.
Training & Education	Certification programme ready for DIH deployment; upskilling materials published open-access
Standardisation	CWA contribution under CEN coordination; gaps identified in data governance standards
Policy Contributions	DATAMITE policy brief submitted; alignment confirmed with EU Data Act and Data Governance Act

Table 1. Exploitation Pathways

3.1. Further Research Pathway

The technical and methodological work produced across the data sharing, governance, and business model strands gives a base for follow-on research. Some topics simply do not fit neatly into one Horizon Europe project, even when the progress is real; data valuation, semantic interoperability, and sovereignty enforcement are good examples. On valuation, the KPI catalogue and the dataset computation method are an initial way of structuring a long-running problem: fair and workable pricing of data assets across different organisations and sectors. It is still unresolved. Further work that builds on these tools, including the LLM-based Retrieval Augmented Generation system delivered in D4.7, could support valuation models that react more to context, demand, and sector, but that remains to be proven at scale. The multi-domain interoperability mechanisms—based on OWL/RDF ontologies, DCAT, ODRL vocabularies, and

the Ontology Alignment Tool—were implemented in pilots and appeared to support cross-domain semantic harmonisation in those settings, even though practical governance assumptions often pulled in other directions. That gap between specifications and day-to-day practice keeps coming up, and it likely warrants more study as the Common European Data Spaces start to see real traffic. The sovereignty components, backed by blockchain/DLT-based persistent usage contracts, also look like areas where extra engineering and testing would pay off, especially given the Data Act, the AI Act, and continued GDPR enforcement shaping expectations. Partners intend to pursue follow-on funding via Horizon Europe Cluster 4, the EIC Transition instrument, and programmes such as INTERREG Europe and Eurostars, using the pilots as the initial evidence base.

3.2. Education and Training Pathway

Long-term uptake of the DATAMITE framework will likely depend on more than software maturity. Teams also need the skills and the internal room to adopt new practices, and that is not always available. So, the project put real effort into training and education, producing two open sets of resources: the DATA Tech Training Materials for deployment and integration staff, and the DATA Business Training Materials for decision-makers who have to make the call on monetising data. Both sets of resources were released as Open Educational Resources under open licences and made available through a Moodle-based hosting environment. The project targets a minimum of 20 technical modules, 10 business modules, and 500 downloads, with hands-on engagement by at least 200 staff members across pilot and partner organisations. Feedback on quality and relevance was gathered as part of the pilot process, with an eye on what works in practice rather than what looks good on paper. Next to the materials, the Training delivery was set up for different contexts: self-paced MooC modules for scale, live workshops for depth, and DevRooms and hackathons at EclipseCon, the EGI Annual Conference, and AI-on-demand events. Partner commitments include OTE-organised workshops for Greek energy and water utilities, CERTH-hosted sessions on data sharing and sovereignty mechanisms, and UCC's ongoing engagement through the International AI Doctoral Academy (AIDA), with 70 member institutions and over 100 lecturers.

#	Course name	Partner	Form of the courses	Start date	Delivery date	Language
1	How to install and use the DATAMITE framework from the user's perspective	CERTH & ITI	Documentation & dedicated meetings	2025-02-01	2025-02-28	English
2	Data governance tools or data governance and quality tools	ITI	Series of short videos uploaded in the Youtube channel in the DATAMITE training pills list	2025-02-01	2025-03-26	English
3	How to deploy and use DATAMITE framework: a step-by-step guide	OTE	Wiki page	2025-02-01	2025-03-28	English
4	Integration of the different modules of DATAMITE in infrastructures (cloud, local or "on premises" deployment)	GiDITEK	Official documentation (internal)	2025-03-20	Continuous	Spanish
5	Enhancing MISTRAL visibility through DATAMITE	CINECA	Live webinar	2025-02-01	2026-01-15	English
6	Pontus-X marketplace course	PSNC	Moodle course with a series of short movies	2026-01-01	2026-03-06	English
7	Publication/User Instructions	1001 Lakes	Publication/ User Instructions	2025-04-01	2025-04-28	English
8	Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Providers	HEDNO	Moodle course	2025-03-15	2026-02-28	English
9	Introduction to Data Spaces for Data Consumers	HEDNO	Moodle course	2025-02-15	2026-02-28	English

#	Course name	Partner	Form of the courses	Start date	Delivery date	Language
10	How to use CI/CD procedures in DATAMITE to commit the codes, from the developer's perspective	CERTH	Moodle course	2025-03-26	2025-12-20	English
11	Unlocking Open Source Potential: DATAMITE's open source guide and how you can contribute	ECL	Live webinar	2025-11-27	2025-09-27	English
12	Data Harmonisation Tools	ICCS	Manual, PPT, Video	2025-02-01	2025-06-17	English
13	DATAMITE Data Preparation and Sharing in the Data Spaces	E-REDES	Series of short movies; Slide deck with Ad hoc presentations	2025-02-01	2025-09-30	English & Portuguese
14	Getting to know the fairness data tool	UCC	Series of short movies	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English
15	Transforming data into impactful products	CERTH	Moodle course	2025-06-21	2025-10-27	English
16	DATAMITE: Sharing Energy Data through Data Spaces for Data-Driven Tools	HEDNO & CERTH	Live webinar	2026-03-16	2026-03-23	Greek

Table 2. Delivered training courses

Figure 3. DATAMITE Training Pills

3.3. Standardisation Pathway

Standardisation can help research outputs last, because it reduces the risk that everyone builds a slightly different version and calls it the same thing. Without that anchoring, fragmentation is a real outcome. DATAMITE addressed this under DIN coordination, starting with mapping standards activity across CEN, CENELEC, ISO, IEC, and ETSI, then checking where DATAMITE outputs sit next to what is already covered, and finally looking for places to contribute. The review highlighted topics like interoperability, quality metadata, data sovereignty, usage control, and governance of data marketplace transactions. These areas are busy, and different bodies are working in parallel, but pilot experience can still help keep the discussion grounded. Where gaps were seen, the consortium considered a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA), because it is open and can be produced in a commercially relevant timeframe, although it still depends on process and participation. Public deliverables such as D1.4, D2.4, D2.5, and D4.6 were prepared at a public dissemination level so they can be used as reference inputs. Continued engagement in the Data Spaces Business Alliance, the Data Spaces Support Centre working groups, and BDVA activity meetings is meant to keep alignment with the Common European Data Spaces as they evolve.

3.4. Commercial Pathway

Making an open-source project sustainable through monetisation is not simple. Adoption tends to require low barriers, and business sustainability tends to require clear value that someone is willing to pay for. DATAMITE's approach aims to hold both, using a layered model in which open

components sit alongside commercial offerings rather than being pushed out by them. It is a balancing act.

The open-source core—Architecture Reference Implementation (KER 1) and the full module suite (KER 2)—is released under the project’s open-source approach. If adoption grows, it should raise visibility, provide a reference that aligns with EU data space architectures, and create an installed base that makes service work viable. Revenue here is usually indirect. It tends to come through consulting, integration, and support, not only software licences.

The Advanced Components (KER 4) target organisations that need more than the open suite can provide in a given deployment, for example, on security, privacy enforcement, anonymisation, or performance. They build on [RADIATUS](#) background intellectual property and include capabilities such as advanced bias detection and integrity verification mechanisms, and they are positioned for commercial licensing. Cost benchmarks matter here: proprietary data governance platforms from Collibra, Informatica, and IBM often carry annual costs of €50,000 to €200,000 or more. Against that, a DATAMITE-based offer may provide EU data space compatibility at a lower cost, depending on what is bundled and how the service is packaged. The business training materials and strategy frameworks under KER 3—including the KPI catalogue, action blueprints, and the data valuation methodology—can be used as open resources. Still, they also translate into advisory work for organisations that need to price data or set up sharing arrangements. The certified Tech Experts under KER 5 sit in the same space, because implementation support and training are what many adopters will ask for first. The go-to-market approach described in the document runs through eight phases, from business model formation to partner buy-in and then consolidation and launch. The six pilots provide cases that help tell the story.

3.5. Policymaking Pathway

DATAMITE sits in the middle of a busy EU policy space on data. The project touches the Data Governance Act, the Data Act, the AI Act, GDPR, and the European Data Strategy, and those frameworks shape what data monetisation can look like in practice. The six pilots, including work in sectors like energy and telecommunications, provide some implementation-backed observations that can feed policy discussions, within the limits of what a project can test. The main policy-facing output is the DATAMITE Insight Paper. It is meant to be short, readable, and actionable, and it summarises what was seen during implementation and what might help reduce barriers around interoperability, trust, and monetisation. Dissemination runs through DSSC channels, Digital Europe programme networks, and partner links. The consortium also

participates in policy-related dialogue through the Data Spaces Business Alliance (co-founded by IDSA alongside Gaia-X and BDVA), the BDVA Data Sharing Spaces Task Force, the Digital SME Alliance's Focus Groups on Fair Digital Markets and Ethical Tech Interoperability, and the European Commission's High-Level Expert Group on AI. Legal and social science expertise from LIF, ZSI, and UCC supports the work, because policy is never only technical.

3.6. Intellectual Property Strategy

DATAMITE aims to maximise the adoption of its outputs by the community while allowing for sustainable commercial exploitation of each of its five Key Exploitable Results (KERs). According to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement Article 16, the ownership of foreground IP will be allocated to developing partners, while broad dissemination through open licensing. This dual approach doesn't only support KER 1, KER 2 for research/technological exploitation and KER 3-5 for commercial pathways, but it also helps to ensure accessibility of the EU data economy, protecting the value of the data innovation. The main open-source license of the DATAMITE open-source portfolio is a permissive one (MIT license) which is optimized for commercial adoption and ecosystem integration. KER 2 (Open-Source Core Suite) and its components are proposed with MIT license to give maximum freedom to Developer and compatibility with enterprise architecture at the same time, while KER 1 (Architecture reference) is proposed with an EPL compliance model with the intention of interoperability of data space. Materials for KER 3 Business utilize Creative Commons BY 4.0 (CC-BY) to create educational materials, requiring acknowledgement. Components KER 4 can be sold commercially as a component with Enterprise SLAs. KER 5 certification is done using proprietary service IP. This governance promotes sustainable growth and protects the commercial interests of partners. The strategy positions DATAMITE happily to be replicated across EU data spaces (IDS, Gaia-X, EOSC). Hence, Pilot validated components are at TRL 7–8 under open license.

The modules of the DATAMITE are released under the MIT License which allows for unrestricted commercial use, modification, distribution and requires the preservation of copyright notices. More information related to the MIT license for DATAMITE components described in the [D6.3](#) (Sections 5.3 & 5.4)

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Figure 4. MIT License Template

DATAMITE component	Copyright Owners
data-governance-backend	ITI
kpi-library	ITI
quality_evaluator	ICCS
user-defined-rules-generator	TECNALIA
access-control	CERTH
policy-library	1001 LAKES OY
brokers-eu-portals	UCC
data-product-composition	CERTH
gaiax-dataproduct-onboarding-ces-publishing	TECNALIA
logging-service-extension	TECNALIA CERTH
policy-engine-extension	CERTH
logging-tool	CERTH
datamite-edc-connector	FRAUNHOFER ISST
data-storage	ITI
infrastructure	ITI TECNALIA
streaming-service	ITI
anonymization-tool	CERTH
trino-tool	CERTH
data-discovery-connectors	ITI
fairness-data-bias	UCC
data-sampling-recommender	TECNALIA
iccs-data-harmonization-tools	ICCS CERTH others
psnc-data-harmonization-gui	PSNC ITI others
mage-tool	ITI
psnc-data-harmonization-tools	ITI PSNC
psnc-data-harmonization-service	PSNC
frontend	LOBA
Backoffice	LOBA others

Table 3. Copyright owners for the DATAMITE framework repositories

3.7. Individual Exploitation Plans

The individual exploitation plans set out in D6.4 were kept in place and then adjusted as validation and refinement work progressed. Based on what the consortium has on record, there were no major structural changes in IP ownership, strategic objectives, or exploitation intentions across the 26-partner consortium. Most updates relate to Technology Readiness Level (TRL) progression, moving from initial TRL 4-5 to validated TRL 6-7 across most components, with several modules approaching TRL 8 readiness for commercial deployment. The pilots helped here by producing feedback and metrics that partners can point to.

Several collaboration opportunities identified during D6.4 have been pursued during the reporting period and, in some cases, further clarified, in particular in relation to:

- Integration services combining the Data Governance Module with the Data Quality Module
- Combined offerings of the Data Sharing Module with the Data Security components
- Training services bundling technical implementation support with business model development expertise

Partners maintain ownership of the foreground IP under the Grant Agreement, Article 16. Joint ownership agreements govern shared results.

ITI – Instituto Tecnológico de Informática (ES)

& Associated partner: UPV – Universitat Politècnica de València (ES)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Open-Source Core Framework (Framework Architecture, Data Governance & Quality Modules, Data Ingestion & Storage Toolset)
- Architecture Reference Implementation (technical implementation of the monetisation framework)
- Consulting & Training Materials
- Engagement with communities sharing experiences from DATAMITE

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Data Ingestion & Storage (~75%)
- Data Discovery Tools (>50%)
- KPI Library (>90%)
- Data Governance Backend (>90%)

- Metadata Repository (>90%)
- Data Dictionary / Data Catalog / Data Glossary (>30%)

Exploitation pathway

ITI plans to maintain the DATAMITE project under the Eclipse Foundation Governance and to continue evolving it. There are several potential exploitation pathways on the table at the moment:

Using the framework in the context of related projects as a tool to enable data space participants or companies that need to manage data. Examples of current projects that could leverage DATAMITE are (European) Deploytour, (National) DITEC, or several regional initiatives.

Use it as background for future R&D proposals, both European and national, in the context of data governance, monetisation and data spaces.

Increase its TRL to offer it to our ecosystem as data management and publication framework and study potential ways of revenue through consultancy, support and assessment services.

Development of additional licensed tools.

Sustainability

As mentioned, ITI will maintain the role of framework coordinator in the post-project open-source community hosted under the Eclipse Foundation. The goal is to evolve the framework with contributions aligned with future proposals participated in by ITI or by other members of the consortium.

Although the main source of expected revenue at the moment is the participation in future R&D projects, offering support or consultancy services is not discarded, especially as the framework increases its TRL.

FHG – Fraunhofer (DE)

& Associated partner: UNIKO – Universität Koblenz (DE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- EDC Source code and components
- EDC Deployment Docker Single, MVP
- Data Governance & quality modules
- Consulting & training materials
- Data monetisation and valuation: frameworks, blueprints, maturity models, business model strategies, KPI catalogue

- Business cases & models for data sharing platforms

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- EDC Sourcecode (95 %)
- EDC Broker/Mapper (40 %)

Exploitation pathway

Fraunhofer ISST ensures that the results of the DATAMITE project are applied in four ways.

1. Internal knowledge transfer: Presentation of the results at in-house events and in bilaterally held discussions with relevant employees.
2. Knowledge transfer to industry: Fraunhofer's mission is to transfer scientific findings to industry. We will use and market the DATAMITE project results in relevant industry projects.
3. Research: The project results also help us in the scientific analysis of past and future projects dealing with the monetisation/valuation and governance of data.
4. DSSC: We have demonstrated how project partners can contribute their results to the DSSC toolbox. Through our close ties to the Data Spaces Support Centre, we also ensure that the project results are considered in relevant developments of DSSC 2.

Additional information regarding the EDC:

- Reuse of source code and software components for the DATAMITE EDC: Source code and software components developed in the project will be reused in the further development and application of the DATAMITE EDC and in related future implementations.
- Reuse and reference implementation of the EDC deployment: The EDC deployment developed in DATAMITE will be reused as an example and blueprint for future deployments in research and industry contexts.
- Testing and experimentation with the EDC: The DATAMITE EDC will continue to be used for testing, validation, and hands-on experimentation to support continuous improvement and practical adoption.

Sustainability

As already described in the “Exploitation pathway,” Fraunhofer ensures the sustainable use of the project results on multiple levels. Through our extensive network, which spans both the public

sector and the entire industrial spectrum (from SMEs to OEMs), we can achieve long-term impact through all the pathways.

FIR e.V. an der RWTH Aachen (DE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Business Model Strategies for data monetisation
- KPI catalogue for data valuation
- Data monetisation strategy consulting frameworks and blueprints
- Legal framework guidelines

Exploitation pathway

FIR an der RWTH Aachen ensures that the results of the DATAMITE project are sustainably transferred into practice and further developed through the following pathways:

FIR an der RWTH Aachen ensures that the results of the DATAMITE project are effectively transferred into practice and further developed through the following pathways:

- Consulting and applied research projects
Initial elements of the DATAMITE results have already been incorporated into selected consulting and applied research projects. Building on this, the results will be further integrated into future projects addressing data monetisation strategies, business model design, and KPI-based data valuation, allowing for their continued application and refinement in real-world contexts.
- Training and executive education
Project outcomes have been partially integrated into FIR's certificate courses and executive education programmes. These contents will be further expanded and complemented by open training materials to support broader knowledge dissemination and capacity building.
- Internal knowledge transfer
Project insights have been shared within FIR through internal formats such as workshops and project exchanges. This internal transfer will be continued to ensure systematic reuse in future projects and services.
- Knowledge transfer through industry networks
The results have been introduced to relevant stakeholders through FIR's industry networks and will be further disseminated and applied via partnerships, working groups, and collaborative initiatives, supporting their uptake in industrial practice.

- Scientific research and publications

The project results are being prepared for dissemination through scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings and will contribute to the academic discourse while strengthening the scientific foundation for future work.

- Follow-up research activities

DATAMITE outcomes are already informing ongoing research activities and will serve as a foundation for future research projects, including Horizon Europe and national initiatives.

- Communication and outreach

Initial dissemination activities, including LinkedIn communication, have been carried out. These efforts will be continued and expanded to increase visibility, engage stakeholders, and support the uptake of project outcomes.

Sustainability

The sustainability of the DATAMITE results at FIR an der RWTH Aachen is ensured through a continuous research-to-application cycle, in which project outcomes are translated into practical solutions and further refined through their application in industrial and research contexts.

The methods, concepts, and frameworks developed within DATAMITE will be sustained through their gradual integration into FIR's consulting and applied research activities. While initial elements have already been introduced into selected projects, their systematic use and further development will take place in future projects, ensuring long-term relevance and practical impact.

The knowledge generated in the project will continue to be transferred through FIR's educational activities. Training materials and project insights will be incorporated into certificate courses and executive education programmes and will be continuously updated to reflect new developments and application experiences.

In addition, the results of DATAMITE will serve as a foundation for future research activities. They will be further developed and extended in the context of national and European research projects, contributing to the ongoing advancement of data monetisation, valuation, and governance approaches.

UCC – University College Cork (IE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

UCC provided management in KERs; technical architecture, business strategy, and expert services. The main outputs consist of co-leading KER 1: Architecture Reference Implementation which delivers deployment patterns compliant with EOSC/IDS, KER 3: Monetising Strategies which delivers data valuation frameworks and KPI catalogues, and KER 5: Tech Experts & Training Services which delivers certification methodologies. UCC delivered pilot-validated tech docs for cloud-native DATAMITE deployments and business model templates tailored for public sector/research orgs. UCC's assets act as a bridge between DATAMITE's technical excellence and real-world adoption in Irish/European research institutions and data-intensive enterprises.

Exploitation pathway

UCC harnesses its unique academic-industry duality for R&D and commercial exploitation. The main route is to incorporate DATAMITE outputs into consulting for Irish Data Spaces (SFI Research Ireland, EOSC synergies) and corporate training programmes for UCC's enterprise partner network. The inclusion of KER 3 material in Data science educational impact as well as MaREI energy research program which is an integral part of curriculum. Then the UCC has become an approved [...] EOSC marketplace publishing reference architectures and Horizon Europe follow-up proposals based on DATAMITE TRL7 validation are secondary pathways. Based on GA Article 16, Foreground IP will use EPL/CC-BY licensing which maximises research dissemination and protects the UCC's methodologies behind the delivery of its services.

Sustainability

UCC's Sustainability makes use of its existing research-to-market translation infrastructure. By virtue of academic continuity, the curriculum is always integrated, and students are involved in extension projects on DATAMITE. Further, due to enterprise partnership, commercial service pipelines are created through UCC (University-Industry Collaboration office). The Horizon Europe CL4 and Digital Europe Programme are essential for the R&D leadership in Data Spaces and AI Governance. UCC's long-term viability is underpinned by its strategic location within Ireland's National Data Strategy and European Open Science Cloud interfacing systems, evolving with research and public sector data monetisation needs.

TEC – Fundación Tecnalia Research & Innovation (ES)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation includes four open-source software modules in three different areas, Gaia-X on-boarding integration, Data sovereignty and observability EDC extensions and Data quality.

- Open-source Brokers and plugins for IDSA/Gaia-X integration. They provide a toolset to facilitate the creation of the Gaia-X models needed for both the data space participant and the data product compliance processes. Besides, the creation of a decentralised identity and the use of the APIs provided by de Gaia-X Clearing House to follow the compliance processes are covered.
- Data sovereignty toolset: open-source EDC extensions for policy enforcement and observability. The policy engine extension provides several policy enforcement capabilities, including purpose, location and time interval restrictions.
- Open-source module for data quality user-defined rules, including DQV extensions. This module allows the user to define specific quality requirements.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Gaia-X on-boarding helper (100%)
- EDC Extensions (100%)
- Data Quality Module (DQM) user defined rules (100%)

Exploitation pathway

TECNALIA exploitation pathways are related to three of the main pathways identified: Research, Training & Education and Commercial.

From the research pathway point of view, TECNALIA will continue using the results in follow-on Horizon Europe proposals in preparation, and National & International funding Schemes. These projects will allow TECNALIA to continue improving an extending the results, reaching higher TRLs. Besides, TECNALIA engagement with IDSA and Gaia-X communities will be used to continue disseminate the results within the data spaces community.

Commercial exploitation path includes the use of the Open-source releases combined with commercial integration support for technology transfer to industrial clients through TECNALIA's applied research services. TECNALIA plays the role of technical provider and facilitator in several

ongoing projects related to data spaces. The knowledge and open-source results on DATAMITE are being used for commercial data space deployments.

Finally, TECNALIA provides theoretical and practical courses and training materials to our customers including Data Spaces general courses along with training on specific topics like data sovereignty, Data Space deployment strategies using EDC and specific sector application of data space technology.

Sustainability

TECNALIA plays the role of technical provider and facilitator in several ongoing projects related to data spaces. Besides, the knowledge and open-source results on DATAMITE are being used for commercial data space deployments. Both research and commercial exploitation paths will allow the future maintenance and evolution of the results.

CERTH – Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (EL)

- DATAMITE Output used for exploitation
- Data spaces technologies, connectors, portal
- Framework Architecture — technical implementation
- Collection of open-source modules for data quality, security, sharing, and governance
- DATAMITE Tools: Anonymisation, Data Product Composition tool, Logging, Trino Connector, Data Sharing Logging and Access Control
- CI/CD procedures
- Training materials on how to use DATAMITE products

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Anonymisation (100%)
- Data Product Composition tool (100%)
- Logging (100%)
- Trino Connector (100%)
- Data Sharing Logging (100%)
- Access Control (100%)

Exploitation pathway

Open-source release; dataspace-related training and consulting; integration of validated modules into future EU research infrastructures and national digital innovation projects; participation in follow-on Horizon Europe projects; Research publications

Sustainability

Within the DATAMITE project, our contribution focused on the design, development, and operationalisation of key technological components that enable secure, trustworthy, and interoperable data sharing within data ecosystems. The work supported the creation of a modular framework that facilitates data management, interoperability, and controlled data exchange across heterogeneous environments.

To support the operationalisation and scalability of the DATAMITE ecosystem as an open-source project, Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) procedures were established. These procedures automate the build, testing, and deployment processes for the various platform components, ensuring reliability and enabling rapid iteration of the developed services. The CI/CD pipelines also facilitate reproducible deployments and simplify the integration of new modules or updates to the framework. Moreover, CERTH and ITI defined the procedures for framework installation and maintenance within the open-source DATAMITE project. Relevant documentation was produced to guide users and developers, including guidelines for:

- [Automated releases](#)
- [Branching strategy](#)
- [CI/CD procedures](#)
- [Installation and deployment](#)

Several functional tools were implemented and integrated into the framework to support the lifecycle of data products within a data space. These include:

An anonymisation tool, developed to enable privacy-preserving data sharing and compliance with data protection regulations.

Data Product Composition Tool, developed to allow users to create and manage composite data products from multiple data sources.

Trino Connector, adopted and extended to enable federated querying and integration across distributed data systems.

Data Sharing Logging was developed to ensure traceability of data access and operations.

Access control mechanisms are implemented through the integration and configuration of a Keycloak instance to support secure data exchange and enforce governance policies within the ecosystem.

In addition, open-access documentation was created to facilitate the adoption and use of the DATAMITE framework and its associated tools.

- [Data Product Composition tool](#)
- [Anonymisation tool](#)
- [Data Sharing Logging](#)
- [Trino connector](#)

Finally, technical documentation, training materials, and guidance resources were prepared to support the adoption and exploitation of DATAMITE technologies. These materials provide instructions on installing, configuring, and using the DATAMITE tools and services, enabling external stakeholders, developers, and organisations to effectively integrate the solutions into their own data infrastructures.

By combining open-source technologies, modular architecture, and comprehensive documentation, the DATAMITE outputs developed through this contribution provide a strong foundation for further exploitation in emerging data ecosystems, supporting secure and trustworthy data sharing across industries and research domains. CERTH aims to further evolve these tools and adopt and exploit them in future research and innovation projects.

ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (EL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Data Quality Evaluator: Tools for metadata extraction, profiling, and quality metric calculation.
- Data Harmonisation Tools: Modules for mapping and aligning heterogeneous data sources to unified schemas.
- Access Control Mechanisms: Integration patterns for secure data access and policy enforcement.
- Training Materials: Training materials and usage guides for the Data Quality Evaluator and Data Harmonisation Tools.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Data Quality Evaluator (100%)

- Data Harmonization Tools (100%)
- Training Materials (100%)

Exploitation pathway

As a non-profit academic institution, ICCS is committed to addressing complex, real-world challenges in order to expand its research portfolio into emerging domains and contribute to the advancement and dissemination of scientific knowledge.

ICCS's exploitation of the DATAMITE outputs aligns with its strategic objectives concerning the development of innovative tools, applications, and services. Through this effort, ICCS aims to further strengthen its research capacity and broaden its expertise, thereby maintaining its leading role in connecting Greek industry with global advancements in science and technology. The project's scientific results will be disseminated through presentations at international conferences and publications in peer-reviewed journals, fostering knowledge exchange within the scientific community while enhancing the visibility and reputation of ICCS and the European Community. In addition, ICCS intends to leverage the experience gained and the tools developed within DATAMITE to support participation in future EU-funded and national research initiatives.

Furthermore, ICCS will emphasise the application, dissemination, and further development of the know-how generated by DATAMITE within educational activities. Established methodologies and existing knowledge, enriched by the project's outcomes, will be integrated into the educational programs of NTUA. Given the advanced nature of the work, these activities will primarily target postgraduate students and participants in continuing education programs.

Hence, ICCS will focus on the advancement of scientific knowledge and the practical application of the DATAMITE results through the following routes:

- Further Research: Publication of the project's findings in peer-reviewed journals and presentation at international conferences. Continuation and advancement of the research themes and further refinement of the developed solutions in subsequent projects.
- Internal Knowledge Transfer: Re-use of the developed modules as a foundational toolkit for future European and national research initiatives in relevant domains, enabling their further advancement and refinement.

- **Collaborative Synergies:** Leveraging of the validated outcomes and contributions to establish new partnerships with research institutes and industrial players focused on similar areas of interest.
- **Curriculum Expansion:** Incorporation of the state-of-the-art methodologies for data harmonisation, quality evaluation and access control into updated academic modules enhancing the quality and relevance of teaching.
- **Training, Education, and Academic Propagation:** Proliferation of the knowledge and expertise gained to the academic community of NTUA, especially postgraduate students at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE).

Sustainability

The sustainability of the ICCS contributions and results is based on a research-to-application cycle, through which scientific knowledge is continuously translated into practical solutions, and subsequently refined through further research and real-world application.

The Data Quality Evaluator and Data Harmonisation Tools will be maintained as functional components within the ICCS internal software repository. In line with the DATAMITE open-source commitment, these tools will remain accessible to the wider community. Their ongoing maintenance and enhancement will focus on ensuring compatibility with evolving data standards, as well as advancing their capabilities, efficiency, and effectiveness through the adoption of emerging software technologies. These activities will be carried out within the context of future research projects and, where applicable, through contributions from the open-source community. Additional knowledge and outcomes generated during the project, such as methodologies and software for secure access and access control, will mainly provide a foundation for subsequent research initiatives.

The Training Materials and Usage Guides will serve as reference resources for integration into future educational activities and courses, and will be continuously updated to reflect new findings and technological advancements. Furthermore, by preserving the technical documentation and deployment guidelines developed during the project, ICCS ensures the retention of institutional knowledge and implementation expertise. The long-term sustainability of these assets will be supported by existing infrastructure, ensuring that the developed software remains stable, accessible, and reusable beyond the project's duration for research, collaborative initiatives, and educational purposes.

PSNC – Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center (PL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Data Support tools (harmonisation pipelines)
- Polish Agriculture Data Space portal (PADS) based on Pontus-X
- Training materials (Pontus-X Marketplace integration)
- DATAMITE framework (multiple deployments for different projects)
- Governance, quality and exploitation of data from the eDWIN platform and the data trading in data markets (PADS marketplace)

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Harmonisation pipelines (100%)
- PADS - custom page design (100%)
- Brokers-EU-Portals - Pontus-X plugin implementation (10%)

Exploitation pathway

The key exploitation pathway for PSNC in the context of DATAMITE project is related to reusing some of its software and data space-related components and resources in further research activities that are already ongoing or are planned in the future, such as other initiatives and projects, both on national and European level.

This includes integration of DATAMITE harmonisation and training tools into PSNC's EOSC-related services as well as usage of DATAMITE components for data spaces connectivity for KMD4EOSC strategic project in Poland. There are several ongoing projects that are part of the Common European Data Spaces. For agriculture it is CEADS (<https://ceads.eu/>) and for the green deal it is SAGE (<https://www.greendealdata.eu/>). PSNC, as a contributor to both projects, will promote usage of DATAMITE data harmonization pipelines and governance tools. In a similar vein, PSNC's participation in follow-on EU research infrastructure projects will provide chance to reuse and further develop chosen components of DATAMITE and be potentially used in academic and research publications.

Other exploitation pathways are linked to PSNC's position and continued cooperation with multiple agricultural entities, such as agencies, institutions and other stakeholders. The PADS will be used to reach actors in agrifood sector in Poland to share their data, with DATAMITE components and framework making onboarding of SMEs and smaller entities much more feasible. The Pontus-X plugin implementation is being already used in other projects (such as CAgrilab)

to facilitate publishing new data. These activities will lead to increased exposure of DATAMITE outcomes to advisory services, Polish research and public sector organisations.

Sustainability

The main sustainability approach of DATAMITE components and outcomes for PSNC is through their reuse and further development in follow-on R&D projects. PADS has already been promoted and is used by a few agricultural projects where PSNC is involved (such as OpenAgri, AgrifoodTEF). The marketplace solutions and Pontus-X integration (PADS, DATAMITE broker implementation) will be further explored to connect within other national and European projects. One of such projects is KMD4EOSC (<https://kmd4eosc.pl/>) - a National Research Road Map Project. Its main goal is creation of Polish universal scientific infrastructure for storage, sharing and efficient processing of large-scale data for HPC, BigData and AI, where DATAMITE solutions are being investigated and are planned to be integrated in context of data spaces integration. DATAMITE data harmonization pipelines are also already reused in Common European Data Spaces initiatives: CEADS and SAGE.

OTE – Organismos Tilepikoinonion tis Ellados (EL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

OTE will exploit a selected set of DATAMITE results that are directly applicable to its internal digital transformation processes, telecom grade data management infrastructure, and emerging data driven service offerings. The key project outputs include:

- Training materials on utilising DATAMITE products, to support internal capacity building and the upskilling of OTE technical, operational and business units in data governance, interoperability and data sharing models.
- Guidelines for nonmonetary benefits evaluation, enabling OTE to assess qualitative and indirect value dimensions associated with data sharing, cross business collaboration, and ecosystem participation.
- Validated cross database interoperability solution, serving as a technical foundation for seamless integration of heterogeneous corporate datasets across departments and legacy systems.
- Data Monetisation Maturity Model (DMMM), used for assessing OTE's organisational readiness for data monetisation and for guiding strategic alignment with emerging internal and B2B data services.

- Business cases & models for data sharing platforms, providing reference scenarios or market positioning, pricing strategies and sustainable operation of data sharing ecosystems.

In addition, OTE foresees substantial future exploitation of the project's Monetization Strategy Blueprint, Data Valuation methodologies, and the broader monetization framework proposed by DATAMITE, which collectively provide actionable foundations for strategic decision making around both direct and indirect data value creation.

Exploitation pathway

OTE's exploitation strategy focuses on both **internal adoption and external commercialisation** pathways:

➤ Internal Integration

- Deployment of **multi-database interoperability tools** within OTE's production grade data infrastructure to enhance consistency, quality and accessibility of corporate data assets.
- Adoption of DATAMITE's **data quality, metadata management, and governance approaches** to support OTE's broader digital transformation initiatives.

➤ Commercial and Ecosystem Opportunities

- **Provision of commercial data interoperability and quality assurance services** to telecom industry peers, subsidiaries, and B2B clients seeking to adopt dataspace aligned architectures.
- Utilisation of the **DATAMITE Monetization Strategy Blueprint, data valuation framework**, and the **DMMM** to design and validate new OTE data driven offerings, including:
 - cross-operator data exchange frameworks;
 - industry data products;
 - monetisation ready APIs;
 - participation in European scale dataspace.

➤ Corporate Training and Advisory Services

Use of DATAMITE training materials and methodologies to expand OTE's **corporate training arm**, enabling provision of data space related training, consulting services and capability building programmes for partners, SMEs, and public sector bodies.

Sustainability

OTE ensures the long-term sustainability of its exploitation actions through:

- **Continued internal investment in digital transformation**, leveraging DATAMITE outputs to modernise data architecture, strengthen governance, and unlock monetisation pathways.
- **Potential licensing of the DATAMITE validated deployment blueprint** to peer telecom operators seeking reference implementations for cross database interoperability and dataspace aligned data management.
- **Ongoing post project collaboration:** After the official end of DATAMITE, OTE will continue discussions with key technical partners as well as with the internal **Data & AI** Units of OTE. These discussions will focus on:
 - advancing interoperability pilots;
 - exploring data monetisation strategies inspired by the DATAMITE framework;
 - assessing further joint deployment or commercialisation routes.

EGI – Stichting EGI (NL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Portals & Data Market Connectors
- Training materials on utilising DATAMITE products
- Data monetisation maturity model (DMMM)

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

- Data market connectors (40%)

Exploitation pathway

EGI plans to exploit DATAMITE results through integration with its existing and emerging service portfolio and through participation in future European initiatives. In particular:

- EGI is currently developing a Large Language Model (LLM) service within the EGI Federation. In this context, the DMMM, together with open-source modules for data quality, security, anonymisation, and the Data Product Composition tool, may be offered as complementary services. These services are particularly relevant for scientific communities interested in deploying AI solutions trained on their own controlled datasets.

- Data Market Connectors and other open-source components developed within DATAMITE are expected to be reused and further developed in future projects funded under Horizon Europe and the Digital Europe Programme.
- The Data Monetisation Maturity Model will be made available through the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub, targeting startups and SMEs interested in improving the exploitation potential of their data assets. The model is also expected to support future European projects requiring enhanced data management and monetisation strategies.
- Training materials on DATAMITE tools will be disseminated within the EGI ecosystem, supporting adoption by research communities, service providers, and other stakeholders.

Sustainability

The sustainability of DATAMITE results is primarily ensured through open-source dissemination and integration within established European research infrastructures.

- The Data Market Connectors have been released as open-source software through the Eclipse Foundation, making them accessible to the wider research and innovation community.
- From EGI's perspective, long-term sustainability will depend on continued adoption and further development through future collaborative projects. As a non-profit organisation, EGI does not pursue direct commercial exploitation of these results. Instead, it supports their evolution and uptake through participation in publicly funded initiatives and engagement with its broad federation of research and technical partners.
- The continued availability and reuse of these assets will be supported by existing EGI infrastructure and community frameworks, ensuring that the developed components remain accessible beyond the project lifetime and can be adapted to new scientific and technological contexts.

AUS – MTU Australo Alpha Lab (EE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

The primary outputs encompass the DATAMITE's communication and dissemination framework, the validated methodology for translating deep-tech and data-driven research into accessible market narratives, and the stakeholder engagement materials (infographics, presentations, and other demo material) created during the project together with the DATAMITE brand identity assets

that were co-developed during the course of the project. These include visual identity guidelines, and audience engagement strategies which tap into the partner network and contact ecosystem developed through the contacts of consortium members, end-users and associated industry stakeholders. AUSTRALO's outputs underpin its value proposition as a specialized marketing and science communication partner for deep science ventures. AUSTRALO was mainly involved in Work Package communications, dissemination and exploitation activities, owning directly or in co-ownership the following assets in DATAMITE such as the communication strategy, the brand identity and visual communication materials, the framework for Stakeholder Mapping & Audience engagement.

Exploitation pathway

By becoming a core partner in DATAMITE, AUSTRALO has greatly enhanced its profile as a deep science marketing specialist within the EU research and innovation ecosystems. The DATAMITE project allowed AUSTRALO to demonstrate its capabilities to transform highly technical data-driven research outputs into messages entirely accessible to non-specialist audiences such as policymakers, infrastructure managers, investors and the public. After the project AUSTRALO can display tangible dissemination metrics (reach, engagement metrics, press coverage, attendance) as your proof-of-concept in your customer acquisition tools. Showcase the DATAMITE partnership in its portfolio as an exemplary deep tech communication case study of Horizon Europe. This branding approach targets a niche, but the growing segment of research-intensive SME's, Spin-Offs, and Innovation Hubs, which possess substantial technical depth but with limited in-house capability to translate this into investor-ready, policy relevant, or market-facing narratives.

Sustainability

The sustainability of AUSTRALO after DATAMITE relies on a diversified revenue and visibility model that will lessen reliance on any individual project or funding source:

- Commercial clients – deep tech SMEs, spin-offs, and scale-ups
- Consortium engagement in future EU project(s) (Horizon Europe, LIFE, Digital Europe)
- Revenue generated by workshops and training delivered through facilitated sessions in research communication and exploitation planning and stakeholder engagement specifically aimed at TTOs, universities and innovation agencies.

It enables AUSTRALO to maintain financially self-sustaining in the long term and remain embedded in the EU innovation and research community.

IDSA – International Data Spaces e.V. (DE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

The interoperability architecture connects the IDS Reference Architecture to DATAMITE's data monetisation framework. The main contributions consist of the harmonization and integration of IDSA components more specifically the IDS connectors, certification tooling, and runtime components with the modules of the DATAMITE core (DGM, DQM, DSEM, DSM, DSTM). IDSA has provided access to state-of-the-art data spaces expertise. Thus, the development of connector extensions is allowing the DATAMITE to be published in IDS-certified data spaces and marketplaces.

The contribution of the IDS Reference Testbed validated the interoperability of DATAMITE over six industrial pilots, providing evidence for the IDS certification at the production-grade level to allow for the adoption of the IDS ecosystem. DATAMITE's outputs are natively interoperable with the leading data space architecture of Europe.

Exploitation pathway

Through its role as the primary governance organization for data spaces in Europe, IDSA engages in Community and Standardisation exploitation in order to maximize the reach of the ecosystem. The Primary Pathway incorporates validated DATAMITE-IDSA connector extensions into the official IDS Reference Architecture and IDS Rule Book. This ensures that DATAMITE remains compatible with all IDS-certified deployments in perpetuity.

Enterprise adoption through certification workshop, listing on Marketplace, technical working group. Only IDSA members can access the global network of 200+ organisations to promote their solutions. The contributions on standardisation are oriented to ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 (AI/data interoperability), CEN-CLC/JTC25 (data spaces), and ETSI technical specifications, which embed the DATAMITE patterns as de facto compliance requirements. The Foreground IP shall follow GA Article 16 with dual licensing (EPL/MIT) which preserves architectural leadership for IDSA while allowing commercial adoption on a broad basis.

Sustainability

IDSA's sustained viability has been made possible through its membership fee structure which provides operational funding for IDSA unaffected by the success or failure of specific projects. As the main community governance body for IDS data space architecture for Europe, IDSA will ensure the continuing maintenance of components with DATAMITE-IDSA interoperability. The

provision of annual reference architecture releases and updated certifications will ensure interoperability of components and solutions from various stakeholders across the whole data space market. Members of the IDSA (industry associations, technology providers, data space operators) keep DATAMITE-certified connectors in constant demand. The long-term viability of DATAMITE depends on the IDSA taking up the core task of coordinating the evolution of IDS in Gaia-X, Catena-X and sector or domain-specific data spaces. The components of the DATEAMITE project will be embedded as architectural standards suggested by the IDSA. Continuous contributions to CEN/ETSI ensure regulatory alignment for continued relevance on the EU Data Act.

LIF – Pravo i Internet Foundation (BG)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

LIF's contributions were crucial to enabling proper regulatory and compliance frameworks within DATAMITE. The main outputs consist of Deliverable 4.6 – Comparative Analysis of Data Sharing Regulation in Europe and its Applicability to DATAMITE context, to establish a full regulatory baseline across EU member states. The complementary exploitable item consists of the Algorithmic Guidance toolkit graphical decision frameworks that orient data types and their corresponding obligations under the GDPR/Data Act, robustness requirements for AI, cybersecurity measures and privacy-by-design principles for practicing use in order to give D4.6 findings practical effect. The LIF developed Pilots Documentation templates (Incidental Findings Policy, Informed Consent forms, Recruitment Policy, NDA agreements) to protect the human rights of subjects involved during pilot validations and the trade secrets of the organizations conducting them. The portfolio of Self-Assessment Templates includes deployable tools regarding Personal/Non-Personal/Mixed Data Processing, AI Robustness Assessment, and Cybersecurity Risk Management, available openly via Zenodo for the widest possible EU reach.

Exploitation pathway

LIF is following a Research + Policy dual exploitation pathway thanks to its unique positioning at the regulatory-compliance nexus of EU data spaces. The primary pathway is targeting consulting services for data space operators, DIHs (Digital Innovation Hubs) and public administration that require support to onboard to regulations for the use of DATAMITE deployment. It includes D4.6 compliance audit of the proposed data sharing and monetization demonstration, algorithms guidance and workshops, and provision of template for self-assessment customisation. Other pathways comprising policy advocacy, or to have LIF materials recognised as de facto standards

in BDVA, IDSA and Gaia-X compliance working groups, and academic integration in Eastern European university curricula tackling the established regulatory fragmentation gap. The LIF is the foreround IP per GA Article 16 which is publicly available under the CC-BY 4.0 license so they can be attributed but the rest of the consulting methodology remains proprietary.

Sustainability

Post-M39 sustainability focuses on three synergistic revenue streams supporting long-term viability. Consulting services target Bulgarian and Greek DIHs implementing DATAMITE pilots, providing regulatory compliance support and template customisation. National funding leverages Bulgarian Ministry of Innovation programmes for public sector digital transformation initiatives. EU policy projects position LIF materials within DG CONNECT framework contracts addressing data space interoperability challenges.

Operational continuity builds on LIF's established regulatory expertise network across Southeast Europe, ensuring replicability within Balkan data initiatives. Long-term sustainability depends on institutional embedding of self-assessment templates within national e-Government frameworks and BDVA i-Spaces certification pipelines. Continuous adaptation to regulatory evolution occurs through annual D4.6 updates coordinated via DATAMITE Open Alliance. LIF maintains single-point authority for DATAMITE regulatory compliance materials across EU-13 jurisdictions.

HEDNO – Diacheiristis Ellinikou Diktyou Dianomis Elektrikis Energeias (EL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- DATAMITE component usage for further research activities
- Guidelines for non-monetary benefits evaluation
- Training materials for utilising data space technologies
- Data monetisation maturity model (DMMM)
- Improvement of internal processes for data ingestion, anonymisation, harmonisation, quality governance, data product composition, and data dissemination to a broader audience of potential data consumers.

Exploitation pathway

HEDNO's exploitation plans cover several aspects:

- **Technical aspect:** The integration of validated DATAMITE data and governance workflows into HEDNO's data-sharing infrastructure, ensuring alignment with open data

policies and interoperability standards, and enabling further contribution to the development of the Common European Energy Data Space.

- **Business aspect:** The development of streamlined and efficient data sharing processes will accelerate the provision of new services and will improve existing ones by fostering collaboration with research partners. Moreover, HEDNO plans to consult the Data Monetisation Maturity Model to assess its monetisation readiness, improve its overall maturity and develop new business strategies to better exploit the monetisation potential of its data.
- **Personnel aspect:** Utilization of the training material developed during the project will lead to personnel upskilling and a broadening of knowledge within HEDNO. Early course feedback indicates an improved awareness of the benefits of Data Spaces and an increased interest in this technology.
- **Research aspect:** The insights gained from participating in the DATAMITE project will be further exploited in future R&D projects that involve Data Spaces.

Sustainability

HEDNO is the sole DSO operator of the Greek distribution network with a substantial infrastructure investment program under regulatory oversight. The company actively fosters research and innovation and implements a wide range of strategic projects, particularly in OT/IT systems, with a strong focus on data management and data governance. It is required to comply with binding EU data regulations and seeks to align with broader EU data policies, principles, and interoperability frameworks.

IDFS – IDFS Sp. z o. o. (PL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- DATAMITE pilot outputs (data sharing platforms)
- Training materials
- Strategies for data monetisation

Exploitation pathway

IDFS leverages the results and expertise obtained from DATAMITE pilots to strengthen its data integration product and consulting portfolio for enterprise and public sector clients in Poland and Central Europe. The approach is multifaceted and aims at continuous, practical exploitation:

- **Commercial integration and service expansion:** Validated pilot environments and components from DATAMITE are incorporated directly into the company's data integration solutions. This enables clients, especially from sectors such as agrifood, public administration, and SMEs, to participate in data sharing processes.
- **Sectoral solution development:** Insights and components from the DATAMITE pilot are extended towards enabling industry-relevant use cases, particularly in agriculture, open data, and digital transformation markets. IDFS platforms such as Agrego, increasingly offer compatibility with data sources and tools supported by solutions such as Pontus-X, benefitting from datasets managed and published in frameworks maintained and developed with the involvement of recognized Polish innovation stakeholders.
- **Advisory and onboarding activities:** IDFS supports the digital onboarding and adoption of DATAMITE-compliant platforms for organizations across sectors. Drawing on practical experience, IDFS enables institutions—such as advisory centers, government entities, and agrifood actors—to integrate data governance and monetization functionalities using proven DATAMITE approaches.
- **Marketplace and data ecosystem enablement:** Platforms offered by IDFS adopt data governance and quality rules, supporting data publication and sharing via digital marketplaces. Where applicable, IDFS will enable clients to utilize open datasets, including those made available via agricultural advisory organizations (e.g., through WODR authored solutions), on sectoral data spaces and multipurpose platforms like Pontus-X, co-developed with input from leading technology partners in Poland.

Sustainability

IDFS ensures the long-term sustainability of DATAMITE results through a multi-faceted approach which leverages ongoing business expansion, active ecosystem engagement and systematic integration of innovative solutions:

- **Ongoing commercial development:** IDFS continues to expand its portfolio of data integration and management services, with DATAMITE-based components and frameworks forming the technological foundation for new products and client offerings.
- **Ecosystem involvement and sectoral collaboration:** Building on the experience gained during the DATAMITE pilot, IDFS is actively engaged with the Polish digital innovation ecosystem and collaborates with sectoral initiatives targeting the agricultural market. We work closely with a broad network of data providers, advisory centers, and market actors,

helping to bridge the gap between cutting-edge data space architectures and real-world business needs.

- **Platform adoption and market enablement:** Platforms such as Pontus-X, integrating DATAMITE outputs, form a key element of our exploitation pathway. By facilitating data sharing, onboarding, and publication—especially in the context of agricultural data spaces—we support the adoption of best practices for data governance and monetisation among Polish and international stakeholders.
- **Exploration of new data-driven business models:** We aim to further develop practical data monetisation models and advisory services for SMEs and sectoral leaders, with particular attention to the evolving needs of the agrifood sector. This includes supporting clients in leveraging marketplace opportunities and unlocking added value from shared data assets.
- **Participation in leading innovation projects:** In addition to DATAMITE, IDFS takes part in forward-looking initiatives such as AgrifoodTef. Our ongoing involvement in national and European R&D programs ensures continuous access to the latest technological advancements and sustained evolution of our service portfolio.

Through this sustained commitment to commercialisation, ecosystem engagement, and participation in strategic innovation projects, IDFS ensures that DATAMITE results remain relevant, accessible, and impactful well beyond the lifetime of the project itself.

GIDI – Gimeno Digital Technologies (ES)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Open-Source Core Framework integration service
- Integration in internal strategy for data sharing/monetisation

Exploitation pathway

DATAMITE is intended to become a key component in the development of the data monetization strategy defined in the internal corporate roadmap. Under this premise, the primary source of exploitation is internal, not only as an entry point within our internal architecture to establish data-sharing channels, but also as a key element for educating and internally disseminating a data-sharing culture.

Although momentum in the field of data sharing is steadily increasing, there is still a certain degree of resistance due to pre-existing cultural inertia. DATAMITE is the essential tool for disseminating this culture across the different departments and companies within the group.

Likewise, as mentioned above, the outcome of the framework integration will serve as the enabling element for the development of a tool to manage potential external data exchanges with other organizations that generate monetary benefits, establishing the essential channels to ensure that such exchanges are carried out securely.

Apart of this, it is relevant the offering of DATAMITE-based data governance and interoperability integration services to manufacturing and industrial SME clients, positioning validated Pilot 1 blueprint as a reference implementation for DIH-supported SME onboarding.

Sustainability

The framework and its integration will be maintained by IT services business. Its updating and evolution come by diverse ways, one of them it's the active participation in the Spanish EDIH ecosystem.

ECL – Eclipse Foundation Europe GmbH (DE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- DATAMITE open-source Framework.
- DATAMITE components as Eclipse Dataspace Component (EDC) extensions.

Exploitation pathway

ECL path to exploitation occurs through long-term sustainability. Eclipse aims to maximize its global developer reach and software community exploitation through governance of its ecosystem and open-source community. Thus, DATAMITE would benefit from a wide availability, a continuous flow of security updates, and strong community contributions. While the DATAMITE framework is already open-source, a transition into a formal open-source project under the Eclipse Foundation would facilitate its sustainability and further exploitation. The incorporation of DATAMITE patterns within EDC reference implementations will lead to the utilization of these patterns in more than 200 dataspace projects.

Sustainability

ECL supports the long-term sustainability of the DATAMITE project through the transition of the DATAMITE Framework from a research project into a formal open-source project under the

Eclipse Foundation. The Eclipse Foundation Framework offers DATAMITE a large community of developers (1M+ developer community), infrastructure, security, governance, release trains and other related services. The integration with the dataspace ecosystem through Gaia-X, IDSA, and Catena-X creates ongoing demand for DATAMITE/EDC extensions. DATAMITE being licensed under the well-known business-friendly open-source MIT license maximises its adoption, contributing to the long-term sustainability.

ZSI – Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH (AT)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

ZSI's primary exploitation focus concerns the conceptual and methodological results generated in DATAMITE on non-monetary dimensions of data sharing and value creation. Central elements include

- the validated SSH framework covering environmental, societal, ethical, organisational and governance impacts;
- the anticipatory foresight approach combining literature analysis, stakeholder engagement and visioning/backcasting;
- the **DATArelect** reflection tool enabling structured assessment of non-monetary risks and benefits.

These outputs are closely aligned with ZSI's institutional profile in social innovation research, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), and governance of digital transformation. The project's findings demonstrate that data sharing is not merely a technical transaction but a socially embedded and context-dependent process, strongly shaped by trust, institutional arrangements and organisational culture. This perspective strengthens ZSI's analytical contribution to European debates on digitalisation, data governance and sustainable innovation.

Exploitation pathway

The validated non-monetary impact framework will be integrated into ongoing and future Horizon Europe and national projects. In particular, it will inform ZSI's work in the *Social Innovation Mission Facility*, where impact pathways and scaling strategies for EU Missions are developed, and in *SI plus – Competence Centre for Social Innovation*, where organisational capacities for social innovation are analysed. In these contexts, the framework will function as a structured analytical lens for assessing societal, organisational and governance implications of data-driven and AI-supported innovation.

The foresight methodology will be applied to further sectoral applications, including digitalisation in long-term care within MAIJobCare, and to mission-oriented transformation processes supported by the *Mission Service Facility*. In these projects, anticipatory stakeholder engagement and visioning exercises provide a structured way to address long-term societal consequences of digital transformation.

The DATAreflect tool will be operationalised as a workshop-based instrument in advisory and capacity-building activities. It can be applied in higher education and institutional development contexts such as *SHER – Sustainable Higher Education and Research in Kosovo*, and embedded in analytical reporting activities such as the *FTB – Austrian Research and Technology Reports*, where systematic assessment of innovation and digitalisation impacts is required. To that end, the DATAreflect tool will be presented and further discussed at various scientific conferences, e.g., the STS NL conference in April 2026.

Sustainability

ZSI will integrate the non-monetary impact perspective into its internal project development procedures. Future digital innovation proposals will systematically reflect the identified environmental, societal, ethical and organisational dimensions in line with RRI principles.

Financial sustainability is ensured through the continued application of these approaches in funded research projects and commissioned studies; no stand-alone commercialisation is foreseen.

The framework is transferable to additional data-intensive domains where trust, governance alignment and organisational readiness are critical. Complementary project results — including training materials, legal and ethical guidelines, and the KPI catalogue with dataset valuation approaches — can be incorporated into capacity-building, advisory and research activities, further strengthening ZSI's analytical toolkit for responsible data governance.

LOBA – Globaz S.A. (PT)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

- Frontend development for the Data Governance and Quality Modules.
- Open-Source Core Framework user interface (UI) components.
- Development of the Backoffice system for generic content management, along with UI/CSS adjustments in Keycloak to ensure visual coherence and a seamless user journey across the platform.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

LOBA does not retain a proprietary, standalone commercial product from this project. Instead, the primary assets are the highly specialised know-how, the capacity building acquired by the development team, and a reusable library of data-oriented UI components. These assets

empower LOBA to expertly bridge the gap between complex deep-tech data systems and user-friendly interfaces.

Exploitation pathway

- **Product Enhancement:** Integration of DATAMITE's governance UI components and best practices into LOBA's existing data management and public administration software products.
- **B2B Services & Customisation:** Offering specialised UI/UX consulting, seamless integration, and premium customisation services (white-labeling) for external companies and public entities looking to adopt the DATAMITE framework.
- **Market Expansion:** Providing commercial support services and tailored frontend development for the open-source community, specifically targeting the Portuguese and Iberian markets.

Sustainability

The expertise gained positions LOBA competitively as a highly capable technical partner (focusing on the "visual layer", usability, and user engagement) for future Horizon Europe, Digital Europe and other funded R&D proposals. Furthermore, the customised support services will generate a continuous revenue stream, ensuring LOBA remains actively engaged with the DATAMITE ecosystem post-project.

WODR – Wielkopolski Ośrodek Doradztwa Rolniczego w Poznaniu (PL)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

WODR provided agriculture-specific capabilities related to data governance and quality rules as well as the publication of data products that were validated in DATAMITE's agricultural pilot. The key results are configurations of the sector-optimised Data Governance Module (DGM) enforcing the Polish/EU standards for Agricultural Data, rule sets for the Data Quality Module (DQM) addressing precision farming measures (soil quality, yield prediction, input optimisation) and integrations of the Data Sharing Module (DSM) for seamless publication to the Pontus-X marketplace. These components are essential for the Polish farmer to monetize field sensor data, satellite imagery, and production records in a GDPR/CAP compliant way.

Exploitation pathway

WODR is pursuing the integration of validated DATAMITE workflows into its core advice services. The main pathway embeds agricultural data governance workflows into WODR's existing farmer

advice services. This will enable data quality assessment and marketplace publication capability for 4,000+ Polish farmers by DATAMITE. Replication targets technology transfer to 12 other EU agricultural advisory centres through EAFRD-funding digital farming initiatives. Sharing of datasets on AgriData marketplaces creates additional revenue from aggregated, anonymised regional agricultural dataset. The Copyrights and Designs Act 1957 prohibits registering a design that is not new or original in that it has been publicly disclosed in India or elsewhere by publication or use.

Sustainability

The sustainability of WODR comes from its public mandate as the agricultural advisory centre of the Warmia and Mazury region which serves more than 4000 farmers in a year. The EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) strategies on digital transformation are multi-annual funding programmes aimed at the adoption of precision agriculture. DATAMITE workflows must be among the essential components of the regional digital farming strategy. The operational continuity of WODR will depend on pre-established farmer networks and integration into the CAP Strategic Plan.

DIN – Deutsches Institut für Normung e.V. (DE)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

The primary exploitation focus of DIN deals with transforming project results into standardisation deliverables. To achieve this, various preparations were made such as a standardisation research which helped to identify which relevant standards have already been developed in order to see whether standardisation gaps exist. The identified gaps were further examined through a standardisation potential workshop to see where the DATAMITE consortium could potentially see a need to develop a standardisation deliverable using the DATAMITE results. The DATAMITE results were used to develop potential ideas for standardisation deliverables such as CWAs. Such ideas were DATAMITE project results regarding data monetization strategies, data quality dimensions and categories and custom metrics for measuring the quality of the datasets, Unfortunately, these ideas did not get transformed into CWAs as the ideas only remained ideas and were difficult to standardise.

Exploitation pathway

The other way of ensuring exploitation of the DATAMITE results regarding standardisation is to contribute to technical committees, where standardisation activities are already happening. Active

contribution of DATAMITE's validated data quality methodology to prepare CWA development did not work out as no CWA was developed after exploring different possible ways. Therefore, this technical input is intended find its way to CEN-CLC/JTC 25 “Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge”. The goal is contribute to ongoing standardisation deliverables to ensure that DATAMITE results find its way into standardisation. Publication of standardisation guidelines for the DATAMITE community are also possible.

Sustainability

DIN's role as Germany's national standardisation body, membership fees, and ongoing participation in European and international standards committees.

CINECA – Consorzio Interuniversitario (IT)

Output used for exploitation

The deployment and testing of the framework helped us to gain knowledge on creating data products, inserting access policies, creating ad-hoc rules to determine data quality and disseminating data assets, with this primarily relating to connecting the in-house maintained platform to AIoD and other European portals. Besides, application of the data monetisation maturity models to assess and evaluate the monetising value of our data assets would provide us with immense opportunities to explore the possibility of using our data assets for business exploitation.

In short, the interlinked aspects that can be exploited are as follows: Connecting the MISTRAL to European platforms (AIoD), Evaluating the quality of observation data, application of Data Monetisation Maturity Model (DMMM) and data valorisation with ad hoc formulations.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

CINECA tested and validated the framework using its operational datasets and quality rules specific to the domain. No ownership of IP is claimed over the DATAMITE framework itself. To improve the framework's potential for practical application and future utility in the weather sector, CINECA contributed domain expertise, test-bed datasets and a validation process.

Exploitation pathway

Testing and validating the quality tagging and AIoD brokering tools ensured the possibility to incorporate the framework into the operational pipelines of the MISTRAL platform, and EOOSC

research data services. Besides, it is envisaged that data monetisation maturity assessment will be an asset that can be used to value the datasets for business exploitation.

Sustainability

CINECA provides operational support, including cloud and HPC infrastructure, for various platforms on different domains. Testing and validating the framework ensured that it could be applied to the operational pipelines of other platforms for measuring data quality.

1001 LAKES Oy (FI)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

1001 LAKES was the principal investigator in building the first maturity model for data monetization (Data Monetisation Maturity Model – DMMM). At the same time, 1001 LAKES took the leadership in leveraging results of the tasks T4.1 (monetisation strategies) and T4.2 (taxonomy model/tool) to develop a business blueprint, a tool to enable companies to lower barriers to enter into the data monetization business. Concretely, the DMMM helps to assess the organizational maturity of a company and identify deficits for filling the gaps. Then, the blueprint proposes prefilled business canvasses for twelve identified strategy archetypes. This facilitates to identify and finalize a data monetisation business case in a guided manner. Finally, the data valuation model gives a reference for identifying a price of a concrete data business product.

This blueprint is a toolset that allows 1001 LAKES to consult companies to enter into the concrete business planning for data business products. As a matter of fact, the blueprint serves as a product itself to 1001 LAKES and as a facilitator for companies and organisations of all backgrounds.

Further, 1001 LAKES has contributed to the development of software modules for enabling compliant data sharing. Concretely, the policy library and policy engine will be used to develop software to automate data compliance by formulating machine readable policies and ensuring the subsequent enforcement of these policies on specific data sets.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

While the IP for the blueprint is owned by the contributing organisations, namely 1001 LAKES Oy, UCC, and FIR, the results are published and licensed for free use under the regulations of Creative Commons 4.0. The IP for software lies equally with the contributing companies, including

1001 LAKES Oy. Also here, the results were made available for free use via GitHub under an MIT license.

Exploitation pathway

1001 LAKES will use the blueprint for advisory services to Nordic and European enterprises on data monetisation business model design and value-based pricing. The DATAMITE blueprints will be integrated 1001 LAKES's commercial data strategy consulting portfolio. As such, 1001 LAKES Oy will serve as a multiplier of the named results of DATAMITE and help to disseminate these tools to European enterprises and organisations.

Sustainability

1001 LAKES's commercial consulting revenues and potential spin-off product based on the data monetisation blueprint methodology. Further DATAMITE tools with contributions from 1001 LAKES include work on a policy library and policy engine. These public domain artefacts are intended for use in concrete implementation projects with enterprises after the classic consulting approach.

E-REDES – Distribuição de Eletricidade S.A. (PT)

DATAMITE Output used for exploitation

In E-REDES' context, the results of the DATAMITE project will primarily be exploited through the operational and methodological insights gained during the pilot. The implementation enabled hands-on experimentation with data product creation, governance structures, user-defined and default quality rules, and the end-to-end sharing workflow via the Opendatasoft Open Data Portal. These activities revealed concrete opportunities to improve existing BI workflows, strengthen metadata practices and align internal processes with emerging European data-sharing standards. This learning-driven outcome positions E-REDES to gradually enhance its data preparation and publication processes and to better anticipate the requirements of future energy data-space initiatives.

Result/Asset contribution (IP ownership %)

E-REDES contributes with operational datasets, domain-specific quality rules, semantic governance assets (domains, glossaries, terms), representative data products and the associated business knowledge used to validate and refine the framework. All contributions remain the property of E-REDES. As a demonstration-focused Horizon Europe action, no exploitable

foreground IP is claimed over the DATAMITE framework itself; instead, E-REDES contributes domain expertise, data structures and validation evidence that strengthen the practical applicability and future replicability of the solution within the energy sector.

Exploitation pathway

The exploitation pathway focuses on reinforcing internal readiness rather than on deploying the DATAMITE framework operationally. The pilot clearly demonstrated the value of structured semantics, quality-aware data preparation and data-product-oriented modelling for improving the clarity, usability and reusability of open datasets. These insights will guide the evolution of E-REDES' open-data publication processes, namely through better metadata, richer datasets and closer adherence to shared data and metadata standards. By internalising these practices, E-REDES strengthens its long-term capacity to participate in European energy data spaces once the supporting tools and ecosystems reach higher maturity, while simultaneously providing a transferable reference model for other Portuguese and Iberian DSOs.

Sustainability

Sustainability is supported by E-REDES' role as a regulated electricity distribution operator, with continued investment in data governance, data quality and open-data publication activities embedded in its multi-annual regulatory programmes. Additionally, E-REDES' participation in European energy data-space governance bodies and sectoral working groups provides a long-term institutional mechanism to sustain and evolve the learnings from DATAMITE, ensuring alignment with emerging standards, regulatory expectations and pan-European data-sharing architectures.

3.8. Business Model Strategies

KER #	Focus	Revenue Model
1	Architecture Reference Implementation	Open-source (no direct revenue) + consulting
2	Open-Source Core Suite	Free core + optional commercial support
3	Business (Monetisation) Strategies	Free materials + paid consulting & corporate training
4	Advanced Components (Support Tools)	Commercial licensing + support subscriptions
5	Tech Expert Services & Training	Consulting fees + training programs + certification

Table 4. KERs' Revenue Models Combinations

Architecture Reference Implementation

Introduction

The Architecture Reference Implementation is meant to be useful in a very practical way: it helps different groups get to “running” faster, and with fewer surprises. For Developers and integrators, the documentation and reference code aim to cut the learning curve, so teams spend less time decoding the architecture and more time wiring modules into real systems; the APIs help here, and the patterns come straight from pilot work. For Decision-Makers, the architecture view makes it easier to judge what is being adopted and what it will touch, and the modular setup supports phased roll-out when a full switch-over is too risky. For organisations, the reference implementation is designed to fit different IT environments, including mixed setups, and it keeps the architecture vendor-neutral, so procurement choices remain open. It is also built around standards, which should help interoperability hold up over time. The reference implementation is intended to lower technical risk and reduce the upfront effort of adoption, enabling organisations to achieve useful outcomes sooner. On the technical side, the Architecture Reference Implementation comprises several artefacts that link together. Some are documents, some are configurations, some are examples.

Market and Adoption

The Architecture Reference Implementation is mostly an enabling asset. It is not usually something you sell on its own, but it can make the other DATAMITE pieces easier to adopt by lowering effort and uncertainty.

The people likely to use it include system integrators and IT consultancies implementing DATAMITE for clients, internal IT teams in adopting organisations, software vendors building compatible solutions, and research groups extending parts of the stack.

Because it is open-source and well-documented, the reference implementation can be especially helpful for SMEs that do not have much spare technical capacity.

Business Model

KER 1 operates under a Research and Technological exploitation model, with the reference implementation released as open-source under the Eclipse Public License.

Figure 5. Business Model Canvas (KER1)

Key Partners: Partners from the consortium will handle the delivery and long-term maintenance of the Architecture Reference Implementation. ITI, FIR, 1001Lakes, UCC, LIF, ZSI and OTE, who contribute their spatial data architecture, API design and open-source governance expertise. The Eclipse Foundation is the primary open-source infrastructure partner where the code resides and the conformance to the Eclipse Public License (EPL). Working with IDSA and Gaia-X will ensure that the reference implementation remains aligned with the evolving European data space

standards. EU Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) networks can help in the dissemination and adoption across regional ecosystems.

Key Activities: The main tasks that support this KER relate to the design, documentation and ongoing improvement of the DATAMITE architecture. Among them are the full specification of system architecture and API interfaces, a reference implementation codebase that is developed and maintained, integration work with IDS and Gaia-X components, and the leveraging of an active open-source community. Other activities include publishing deployment configurations, sample code and integration patterns based on the six pilot implementations to ensure that the reference implementation reflects real-world, production-proven architecture decisions.

Key resources: The main knowledge assets supporting KER 1 are the consortium's knowledge of the principles of the IDS Reference Architecture Model (RAM) and the background experience of the partners from earlier ICT-13 projects (DataPorts and DataVaults). The DATAMITE architecture is constructed based on these contributions, which are mature and tested. The primary base of the technical resources includes the open-source architecture blueprints, API specifications, and deployment configurations hosted on GitHub and Eclipse. Complementing the codebase are both developer documentation and integration guides to help external adopters integrate with ease.

Value Proposition: The Architecture Reference Implementation offers a great deal of value to its audience with its multiple layers. Developers and system integrators save a lot of time and technical risk as they do not have to design their architectural foundations from scratch. It is a vendor-neutral, modular and standards-based blueprint that enables phased adoption without proprietary lock-in for decision-makers. At the level of the ecosystem, the open-source reference architecture has the potential to position DATAMITE as the de facto standard for EU data monetisation platform interoperability with IDS, EOSC, and Gaia-X. Due to the fact that an architectural framework of the system has already been validated with a relevant pilot application, it can also serve as a reference architecture to support the deployment of future EU data spaces.

Customer Relationships: Customer engagement for KER 1 is primarily community-driven and self-service in nature. Developer documentation, tutorials, and architectural guides are made openly available to enable autonomous adoption. GitHub issue tracking and community forums provide responsive peer and partner support, while technical workshops and webinars organised by DATAMITE and BDVA community channels enable deeper engagement for complex

integration scenarios. Tech Experts serve as a complementary relationship layer for organisations requiring bespoke architectural guidance or production deployment support.

Channels: The Architecture Reference Implementation is available mainly through GitHub and the Eclipse Marketplace in the global open-source developer community. The EOSC portal and AI-on-Demand platform aim to reach the research and institutional audience. Participation in BDVA community events and publishing in scientific papers in data management and digital transformation venues are important for building awareness and credibility. The DATAMITE Open Alliance site is the central repository for all documentation, pilot reference implementations and contact points for potential adopters.

Customer Segments: KER 1 is primarily aimed at tech providers and platform developers looking for a proven architecture for data monetisation solutions. It is also targeted at research and technology organisations (RTOs) that are building or extending data space capabilities. Open-source developers play a key secondary role in improving and extending the reference implementation within the community. EU data space architects, whether in large companies, public administrations or DIHs, represent the third category of stakeholders looking for interoperable blueprints compliant with standards for deploying European data infrastructures.

Cost Structure: The majority of KER 1 costs are R&D and knowledge-management related. The ongoing work effort to maintain and update the architecture documentation and reference codebase, for IDS, Gaia-X, EOSC, as the relevant standards evolve. Open-source community management, including triaging issues and coordinating contributors. Hosting infrastructure to run the reference deployment and testing environments. Training and certification material development in line with the architecture. The costs will be borne by the lead partners (FIR, 1001Lakes, UCC) while participation in standardisation activities and follow-up research shall partially offset them.

Revenue Streams: In accordance with its Research and Technological exploitation model, KER 1 is not a source of licensing revenue. The strategy for releasing open source prioritises adoption and ecosystem positioning over monetisation. The consortium partners will provide organisations that adopt the framework with professional services, mainly architecture consulting, custom implementation support, and deployment optimisation engagements. It is through this professional service provision that they generate indirect revenue. By technical and business training programmes (in line with KER 5) and by confirming competitive advantage by the

reference implementation for follow-up proposals for funding Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programme.

Open-Source Core Suite

Introduction

KER 2 is a toolset designed for all organisations, from SMEs to large enterprises, that require a production-grade, modular toolset for governing, assessing, securing, sharing and trading their data assets. It has five integrated open-source modules (DGM, DQM, DSEM, DSM, DSTM). These can be used individually or together, making them available to organisations at all stages of data maturity. The suite aims to mitigate the cost and vendor lock-in barriers that have historically prevented European organisations from fully engaging in the data economy.

Market and Adoption

The primary players in the data governance and quality tools market are proprietary vendors such as Collibra and Informatica. Their licensing cost tends to be above €50,000 per year, thereby making effective data monetisation tooling affordable only to big European firms. This gap can be addressed by KER 2, which will have early adoption concentrated around SME with DIH networks and research-oriented organisations within the EOSC ecosystem. Testing across six industrial sectors demonstrated production reliability at TRL 6-7.

Business Model

KER 2 is released as free open-source software, as community adoption is the primary indicator of its success. Optional support contracts, advanced feature subscription, and downstream consulting and training demand under KER 4 and KER 5 are the sources of commercial revenue.

Figure 6. Business Model Canvas (KER2)

Key Partners: The lead of the task is ITI and supported by CERTH, ICCS, LOBA, and TEC. The partners collectively possess the main software development contributions across the five main modules. IDSA will specify the connector and provide rulebooks for secure data exchange. The Apache Foundation could provide basic open-source components like Atlas, Ranger, and Trino, which will provide the technical substrate for the Data Governance and Data Quality modules. The Eclipse Foundation oversees the infrastructure for release, licensing and general availability as an open source, with respect to long-term support of the community.

Key Activities: The main activities for KER 2 are based on a complete end-to-end software development lifecycle of the five principal modules, namely: the Data Governance Module (DGM), Data Quality Module (DQM), Data Security Module (DSEM), Data Sharing Module (DSM) and Data Sharing and Trading Module (DSTM). Development tasks involve connecting with diverse storage technologies (PostgreSQL, MongoDB, MariaDB), implementation of FAIR compliance across the data lifecycle, and continuous integration and automated tests for production-grade quality. Other ongoing activities include interoperability validation against the specifications for IDS and Gaia-X connectors. As well as solving community issues, the periodic release of new features is based on the feedback from early adopters of the six pilots.

Key resources: The essential technical building blocks of the suite are based on a robust set of open-source components. Apache Atlas for data cataloguing, Apache Ranger for access policy

enforcement, and Trino for cross-database query federation. The infrastructure for the sovereign exchange of data is provided by the IDS connectors and Gaia-X components. The IDSA Rulebook and the SITRA Fair Data Economy Rulebook provide the governance and compliance logic across modules. The extensive expertise of the partners in implementing multi-domain data portals like EOSC and OpenAIRE provides a proven operational knowledge that has informed the architecture and integration pattern of the suite.

Value Proposition: The Open-Source Core Suite is a production-hardened offering for the complete data monetisation lifecycle, available at zero licensing cost. This represents a credible alternative to proprietary offerings such as Collibra or Informatica, which cost more than €50,000 per year in licensing alone. An organisation can use individual modules one at a time or can use the full suite together, thereby minimising implementation risk and allowing for incremental capability development. The suite's built-in FAIR compliance and effortless interoperability with IDS, Gaia-X, and EOSC make it the most accessible and standards-compliant open-source solution available today for European organisations that want to participate in the data economy.

Customer Relationships: Customer engagement is done in a community-driven and open-source way. Customers can raise issues via GitHub issue tracking. They also use developer forums. The company provides responsive technical support on these platforms. For those in need of a more formalised approach in their operations, Certified Tech Experts that operate through the KER 5 service offering provide support contracts and implementation support. The MooC-based training modules developed under KER 3 are supporting the technical relationship layer by enabling self-paced upskilling of technical operators and business users. The multi-tier relationship model allows the suite to be obtained by resource-constrained SMEs and the service-level expectations of larger enterprise adopters to be met.

Channels: The Open-Source Core Suite is primarily distributed via GitHub and the Eclipse Marketplace, where it will be discovered by the world's open-source developers. The EOSC portal and AI-on-Demand (AloD) platform further the reach to academic and research-oriented adopters, and the EU DIH network distribution channels facilitate the onboarding of SMEs with limited technical capacity. The BDVA community acts as a prime channel for awareness and engagement, connecting the suite to the wider European data and AI ecosystem. DATAMITE Open Alliance's website consolidates all release documentation, pilot reference implementations and partnership opportunities in a single entry point for prospective adopters.

Customer Segments: KER 2's two core customer segments are SMEs who want low-cost and modular data monetisation tools without any proprietary licensing costs, as well as large enterprises in energy, telecom and manufacturing seeking production-grade data governance and quality capabilities. Digital Innovation Hubs are important intermediaries that help onboard and support clusters of low-tech SMEs in their regional ecosystems, called deployment intermediaries. The data stakeholders, namely data providers, consumers and brokers, form a fourth segment whose participation in European data spaces depends on the type of compliant and interoperable tooling provided by KER 2.

Cost Structure: The main cost drivers for KER 2 will be software development/maintenance, that is the continuous engineering effort to enhance and stabilize the five core modules, integrate new connector and interoperability specifications, and accommodate the evolution of infrastructure dependencies. The integration and testing costs relate to operating the continuous integration pipeline, cross-module compatibility validation, and performance benchmarking against production-scale datasets from pilots. Costs related to community support effective management of issues, updating documentation and coordinating with contributors. Rephrased - As the suite matures and rises in adoption, the maintenance and security update cycles will represent a relatively higher share of the overall cost base, to be sustained through the commercial service revenues under KER 5

Revenue Streams: KER 2 uses a free open-source design to keep community adoption and ecosystem positioning a priority. The core suite does not carry any licensing fees but reaps indirect revenues from the optional commercial support contracts that its members' technology partners offer to organisations requiring guaranteed response times, prioritised security patching, and specialist technical support. A subscription model for premium features and integrations, such as enhanced security modules and high-performance analytics extensions, adds another revenue stream targeting technically mature adopters. The commercial revenues described here support the sustainability model outlined in Pillar 1. Demand for consulting, training, and deployment services delivered under KER 4 and KER 5 is driven primarily by KER 2 uptake.

Business Model (Monetising) Strategies

Introduction

KER 3 is aimed at business leaders, data planners, and operational managers who have a requirement for structured, actionable frameworks for monetising their data assets but lack the strategic insights to do so independently. The document outlines a platform that offers a set of

open-source business materials. Also, they include strategy profiles, a set of KPIs for data valuation, action plans ready-made for specific situations, and MooC based training modules. All of these will be a tool to turn complex concepts regarding the data economy into accessible and practical action for businesses of any size or sector.

Market and Adoption

Data monetisation business guidance European market is very fragmented, and mostly un-addressable for SMEs. Usually, structured strategic support is only possible via costly management consulting. KER 3 fills this gap through the provision of open-access materials that are calibrated to the unique context of European organisations. By the time of writing, the EUHubs4Data course catalogue already established some early traction, and there are early results from the training programmes of the EU DIHs. This traction is largely coming from the uptake of the courses from first-time entrant SMEs and public sector organisations to the data economy.

Business Model

KER 3 has adopted a freemium model; it distributes its core training materials, strategic frameworks, etc. as Open Educational Resources (OER) free of cost. Revenue comes from consulting assignments for strategic implementation, customizing action blueprint development, and running corporate training programs.

Figure 7. Business Model Canvas (KER3)

Key Partners: The DATAMITE Monetising Strategies materials activities are organised FIR, with contributions from OTE, 1001Lakes, ZSI, AUS and UCC – partners with complementary expertise in data valuation methodologies, business model design, social science impact analysis and open educational resources. BDVA's main unique selling point is its expertise on business models, which acts as a dissemination multiplier via its European data community networks. The EUHubs4Data DIH network is expanding the transfer of training and strategic materials to the regional SME ecosystems of Europe. The engaged academia ensures methodological rigour in the materials developed and embeds them into formal education curricula.

Key Activities: Main activities of KER 3 will involve the research, design and ongoing refinement of structured business strategy frameworks for data monetisation. This includes developing a comprehensive framework for a business model strategy, creating a catalogue of KPIs that allows organizations to measure the quantitative and qualitative value of their data assets, and producing situation-specific action blueprints (e.g DMMM) guiding EU companies in practical monetisation decisions. Analysis of the impact of SSH is designed so that the frameworks capture value dimensions that go beyond money. The strategic resources will be converted into self-paced adaptable formats for training material creation and MooC development suited for audiences ranging from technical professionals to managers and policy makers.

Key resources: KER 3 is based on the Business Model Canvas methodology but extended for data-related contexts and coupled with the existing research on data monetisation that served as building blocks for the strategy profiles and KPI frameworks developed in this project. Algorithms for Key Performance Indicator computations build the quantitative framework for data valuation exercises. Value-based pricing approaches guide organisations when setting prices for data products and services. An LLM-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation RAG system boosts the accessibility and responsiveness of the knowledge base, enabling users to query the strategic material with contextual relevance and situational specificity.

Value Proposition: KER 3 fills a gap in the European data economy and does so in a way which is critical and underserved. It is to provide organisations who wish to monetise their data. The data monetisation strategy profiles have been created to help business leaders choose the best exploitation route for their organisation, situated in varied organisational contexts. The KPI catalogue offers a standardised basis for fair and transparent data valuation. Situation-specific action blueprints turn strategic insight into operational plans. The KER 3 Project provides all of its core materials as open educational resources (OER). This directly tackles the skills gap (unfilled

data economy posts) in Europe. The SSH analysis captures the full value of KER 3's impact which includes not just economic returns but also social/institutional.

Customer Relationships: KER 3 has designed in consultation with customers open, self-service learning models for engagement. Training materials are published as Open Educational Resources (OERs) so that any person or organisation may access them on their own, without the need to go through an institution. Self-paced training modules based on MooC provide users with structured learning routes requiring guidance through the strategic frameworks. Workshops and webinars offered through BDVA events, DIH networks and DATAMITE Open Alliance activities will allow groups and organisations to interact and can be used for collaborative learning or validation of their monetisation strategies. Tech Experts offer consulting services tailored to the needs of an organization, establishing a direct line between the open resource layer and commercial engagement.

Channels: The main distribution channel of KER 3 materials is the DATAMITE repository, MooC Platform and in the future the EUHubs4Data course catalogue which provides direct access to the SME-oriented DIH ecosystem throughout Europe. The AIDA Educational Resource Repository also can be used to reach out to the research community of the AI and data economy. The DATAMITE project website and associated learning platforms will be the central point of public access to all training content. The EU DIH training programs offer a streamlined deployment process by integrating KER 3 materials into ongoing regional upskilling and digital transition initiatives. These channels of distribution will ensure that the strategies and training materials reach the entire target audience – individual practitioners, SME managers, policy analyst and academic researchers.

Customer Segments: KER 3 is for business executives and decision-makers who seek actionable strategic advice on how to start or scale data monetisation in firms. Data-oriented strategists and analytics types form a second segment that needs some structure for turning data assets into money. The EU companies particularly at the early-stage data economy adoption level are the broadest segment looking for practical blueprints that simplify entry into data markets. Because SMEs are much more affected by the skills gap and have limited ability to commission bespoke consulting services, we see them as a priority sub-segment. The fifth segment consists of policy-makers and public sector stakeholders, who use the frameworks and SSH impact assessments for their regulatory and investment decisions in the European data economy.

Cost Structure: The main costs for KER 3 are for research and methodology development, notably the design, validation and iterative enhancement of strategy frameworks, KPI catalogues and action blueprints through workshops, pilot feedback and market consultative. The second biggest cost item is the creation of training materials, including authoring, graphical design and peer reviewing of MooC modules, and interactive learning. Hosting and maintenance costs of the MooC platform cover the technical infrastructure required to enable access, tracking of progress and updating content by the learner. The cost of organizing workshops, including preparing the facilitators, organizing logistics, and documenting the workshop, is a recurring operational cost that is associated with the continuous dissemination and validation of the strategic material.

Revenue Streams: KER 3 has adopted a freemium dissemination model which involves offering core training materials and strategic frameworks for free as open-source materials so as to reach wider use for greater impact on society. The consulting for strategy implementation where the consortium partners and Tech Experts help organisations apply the frameworks on their data assets in their market context generates commercial revenue. The creation of a custom action blueprint, tailored to the sector, maturity level, and strategic priorities of each organisation, is a higher-value service. Corporate training programmes, offered on a contract basis to firms and public administrations striving for structured data monetisation capability development, create another revenue stream that scales with the growing demand for knowledge of the data economy within European industry.

Advanced Components (Support Tools)

Introduction

KER 4 is designed for businesses and regulated industries whose data management needs in term of scale sensitivity complexity of compliance and operational performance exceed the capacities of the open source core suite. A suite of premium commercial modules extending KER 2 with advanced anonymisation, bias detection, privacy enforcement and high-performance analytics capabilities. The advanced components are available for purchase and integration separately, allowing organizations to upgrade their DATAMITE deployment without replacing anything.

Market and Adoption

Firms are facing pressure to improve their data security and ensure compliance by using new tooling. GDPR, the Data Act, and different sector regulations are all more in focus these days. There is a significant market for premium data governance and privacy technologies as

organisations in regulated industries look for alternatives to legacy proprietary solutions that are becoming increasingly misaligned with European data sovereignty principles. Multiple large enterprises in the energy and telecommunications sectors have already approached the KER 4 team, initiating procurement discussions in M19–M39 as part of the go-to-market phase.

Business Model

KER 4 uses a commercial exploitation model generating income through module licences, annual support subscriptions, custom development contracts, and SLA premium fees. The commercial model is designed to support investment in advanced R&D to maintain the sustained elite capabilities that are enterprise-grade.

Figure 8. Business Model Canvas (KER4)

Key Partners: The Advanced Components are developed and commercialised by ITI, with technical contributions by CERTH, FHG, TEC and ICCS – all partners with the specialised IP, engineering ability, and domain knowledge required to develop and maintain high-end modules unsuitable for the open-source core. Commercial users who demand advanced features can serve as both customer and co-development partner. This allows us to be sure of what capabilities are needed and why. Solution providers with sectoral focus strengthen the partner ecosystem, expanding penetration into vertical areas where custom integration and domain expertise are pre-requisites for usage.

Key Activities: The main activities assigned to KER 4 consist of developing new modules, which add specialised technical functionality to the DATAMITE core and are not available in the open-source release. This incorporates the development and execution of customisations tailored for specific industries, designed to meet the sector-specific data management and compliance needs of energy, healthcare and finance. A key activity stream involves strengthening and improving security, anonymisation, bias detection, privacy enforcement, as well as access controls and other mechanisms. To ensure scalability and throughput levels demanded by large enterprise deployments, optimise the performance of the advanced components. Management of commercial licensing, including contract structure, IP rights, SLA management, etc., is at the commercial delivery model.

Key resources: KER 4 implements [RADIATUS](#) background IP provided by ITI. RADIATUS provides the core technology for some of the advanced anonymisation and security components. Sophisticated anonymisation algorithms encompassing differential privacy, k-anonymity, and pseudonymisation are another important resource enabling organisations to share and trade sensitive datasets in compliance with GDPR and sectoral regulation. The core suite's data quality and governance capabilities have been expanded to include bias detection and privacy enforcement technologies. Powerful data analytics tools are deployed to offer the computing infrastructure necessary for a large business to analyse data at scale across a range of heterogeneous sources.

Value Proposition: The KER 4 provides capabilities that go meaningfully beyond the open-source core. It is designed for organisations whose data management requirements in terms of scale, sensitivity, regulatory exposure or operational complexity exceed the limits of KER 2. The enhanced security and privacy features are designed to respond to the compliance obligations of regulated industries, where the business costs of inadequate data protection mean financial and reputational damage. Industry-specific enhancements lessen integration efforts and time-to-value for businesses deploying DATAMITE in specialised operations. High-volume enterprise data pipelines require throughput and latency, which premium performance and scalability can address. Service reliability assurances that enterprise procurement processes require are provided by commercial support arrangements and SLA-backed guarantees.

Customer Relationships: The customer engagement of KER 4 works through an enterprise-oriented relationship model designed to meet the service expectations of large companies. We have dedicated enterprise sales and account management teams who guide prospective

customers through assessment and purchasing. Technical support is separate to community-based support available for KER 2. It delivers timely, expert assistance for complex integration and operational scenarios. Custom development services help organisations to order extensions or adaptations of the advanced components based on their own technical architectures. Guaranteeing uptime via SLA creates a formal commitment to reliability that ultimately informs the decision to deploy an enterprise. The agreement also provides the framework from which ongoing support revenue flows.

Channels: Most enterprise sales are done directly through the consortium technology partners and prospect customers are either reached out to directly, through industry events and referrals from the DATAMITE Open Alliance network. A partner reseller network allows opening up markets and sectors where consortium partners lack a physical presence. Industry-specific distributors provide localised commercial and technical support in vertically specialised domains. EU DIH commercial services provide a facilitated procurement solution for organisations in DIH ecosystems requiring advanced capabilities which cannot be delivered through the standard SME onboarding offering. Together, they ensure that the sophisticated components reach enterprises and regulated industries where they provide the maximum value.

Customer Segments: The main customer segments for KER 4 are large companies in the energy, telecoms and financial industries. These industries typically process substantial data loads, operate under sophisticated regulations, and have the organisational capacity to afford high-quality software capabilities. Organisations with complex data needs, such as those working across several jurisdictions or integrating data from highly heterogeneous sources, make up a second group whose needs systematically exceed the open-source core capacities. Industries that are regulated – especially healthcare and financial services – represent an important section where the KER 4's advanced security of encryption, anonymisation and compliance features meet strict regulatory requirements. There is a 4th segment comprising high-security requirements sectors where enhanced privacy enforcement and access control capabilities shall be a prerequisite. The example here is defence-adjacent, critical infrastructure, etc.

Cost Structure: The cost structure of our KER 4 is predominantly driven by advanced R&D – the ongoing engineering investment to develop, validate and maintain premium modules at a standard and level of security required by enterprise customers. Costs for custom development involve bespoke work that enterprise customers commission to adapt the advanced components to their own technical environments. The ability to support commercial clients with complex,

urgent technical problems through a dedicated enterprise support team represents a high operational cost that scales with the number of commercial clients served. Sales and marketing functions, enterprise outreach, conference attendance, account management, etc., which incur further costs necessary to maintain and grow the commercial pipeline, are another cost bucket. Costs of commercial infrastructure, covering the licensing management system, SLA load monitoring tooling, and secure delivery environments, complete the cost base.

Revenue Streams: KER 4 has a fully commercial model with four interrelated revenue streams. It can earn money through licensing commercial modules to organizations to obtain usage rights to individual advanced components or to the entire premium suite based on the scale and scope of implementation. Technology companies benefit from the recurring revenue generated from annual support subscriptions from enterprise customers. This ensures the ongoing maintenance and updates of the technology stack. Customers also get dedicated support for handling any issues or queries that may arise in their operations. A custom development contract is for the commissioning of bespoke integrations, adaptations to specific sectors, or the extension of new capabilities. It leads to project revenue and assists in building advanced componentry. SLA premium fees generate an additional revenue stream by offering enhanced uptime guarantees as well as priority response times and dedicated escalation support for customers needing the highest standards.

Tech experts & Training Services

Introduction

KER 5 is specifically designed for any business interested in deploying, integrating, or extracting value from DATAMITE technologies through expert-guided support. It provides a structured certification programme that produces Certified Tech Experts and Tech Trainers, along with a portfolio of consulting, implementation and corporate training services. It connects the availability of DATAMITE tools to an organisation's ability to effectively use them in order that their adoption translates into measurable operational and business outcomes.

Market and Adoption

The European data economy faces a well-documented skills shortage of 759,000 data-related jobs. These figures are creating a structural barrier to technology adoption at scale. KER 5 eliminates this gap through the creation of a certified practitioner network for expert deployment and training services across the DATAMITE ecosystem. The early demand has been validated

via the DIH service agreements with pilot partners and consulting activities by pilot partners in the later stages of the project.

Business Model

KER 5 with its commercialised path, with revenue from consulting fees, training programme fees, long-term support contracts, and certification fees. The model's service is designed to scale with the growing certified expert network. It will lessen reliance on direct delivery from the consortium as adoption takes off.

Figure 9. Business Model Canvas (KER5)

Key Partners: The consortium delivered KER 5, with the ITI, PSNC, and UCC being the lead service delivery partners. The BDVA i-Spaces certification model is the credentialing framework underpinning the Tech Expert and Tech Trainer certification programmes, adding external credibility and recognition at the European level to the qualification pathways. The training programs designated as EU DIH are regarded as institutional partners that implement the certification and upskilling offer within regional digital transformation ecosystems. The IDSA Data Sharing Winter School expands DATAMITE capacity-building activities to the European data space community and associates certified experts with the IDS standards landscape.

Key Activities: KER 5 implements and runs the certification programs for Tech Expert and Tech Trainer. These are structured qualification pathways for consortium and third-party professionals that will enable them to acquire the skills necessary for deploying, integrating and supporting the

DATAMITE framework in production. The certified Tech Experts provide consulting and support services which turns these skills into direct value for clients through help with hands-on implementation, technical troubleshooting as well as advisory engagements. Corporate or organisational training delivery allows organisations to develop internal capability through customised programs. The ability to transfer knowledge to third parties, such as DIHs, academic institutions, and associations, enables scalability and reach beyond the certified expert network with reference to the consortium.

Key resources: The key input for KER 5 is the pool of Tech Experts and Tech Trainers who have completed the DATAMITE certification programme and who are entitled to implement and train on behalf of the network. The technical as well as business IP created across KERs 1-4 is the knowledge base used for all service delivery so our expert engagements are anchored on production-validated, standards-aligned content. A technical implementation and business strategy training materials that will be developed under KER 3 are the curriculum infrastructure for the certification and corporate training activities. The certification framework and MooC platform for BDVA i-Spaces complete the resources continually to provide the institutional and digital infrastructure for scalable expert development.

Value Proposition: KER 5 seeks to address the implementation gap in an organisation's decision to adopt DATAMITE in its independent capacity to do so without an external partner. Qualified DATAMITE specialists ensure effective installation for businesses, which in turn reduced integration risk as well as outcome time for technical and strategic integration. Customised consulting based on corporate requirements helps ensure that the engagement is not generic and reflects the customer's data assets, infrastructure constraints and business objectives. Through hands-on implementation support and tailored training programmes, we build internal capability to reduce long-term dependence. The onboarding of SMEs through DIHs, alongside the project, benefits smaller organisations that would typically not benefit from deployment expertise support. This illustrates the commitment of DATAMITE to inclusively engage all in the European data economy.

Customer Relationships: In KER 5, we build a professional engagement based on direct contact and trust. Consulting engagements serve as the primary model of interaction in which certified Tech Experts work with client teams. Long-term support contracts are arrangements with organisations that require ongoing technical support after deployment. Collaborating on training programmes with DIHs, universities and the corporate L&D function establishes institutionalised

relationships of recurring demand for both the certification programme and the expert network. Through the service agreements of DIH services, KER 5 is embedded in the service catalogue of the regional innovation hubs to ensure that SMEs can rely on these assets during their long-term development. As such, they can be upscaled in a consistent way in the priority geographies of DATAMITE.

Channels: The main distribution channel is the individual experts are the direct points of contact for the potential clients through their networks and institutions. The aggregated services offered by different Digital Innovation Hubs are displayed in the service catalog. These services can be accessed through the catalogue. The partner organization provides a means of extending market reach into sectors and geographies that are not directly covered by the core expert network. This can be through consortium members and/or affiliated technology providers. The DATAMITE community referrals, as generated with the help of Open Alliance and GitHub community, will create an organic demand channel (through the credibility and trust engendered by open source adoption).

Customer Segments: The main target of KER 5 is organizations that are using DATAMITE and that seek expert guidance to master the technical complications of implementation, integration and optimisation. Implementation support for SMEs is a high priority sub-segment in particular DIH ecosystem onboarded SMEs where internal IT capacity is limited. The second important commercial segment are enterprises who require a custom integration of the DATAMITE modules with existing data infrastructure. Such deployments involve high engagement value and lengthy contract durations. A fourth segment comprises the DIHs which serve regional SME ecosystems. They purchase consulting and training services on behalf of their members and initiate DATAMITE competence building in their general support for digital transformation.

Cost Structure: Most of the costs of KER 5 relate to the development of the certification programme, which includes the design and piloting of the qualification pathways for the Tech Expert and Tech Trainer, the examination and accreditation processes. The costs that relate to expert training and onboarding is the delivery of certification cohorts which includes facilitation and assessment and ongoing pd. The MooC platform, certification tracking system, consulting coordination system, and other service delivery infrastructure represent a recurring operational cost, the costs of which scale with the number of experts in the network. The marketing and sales activities, as well as showcase events, case study development and management of DIH

partnerships, are essential to ensure a pipeline of client engagements and expert candidates, which is necessary for the commercial viability of the service model.

Revenue Streams: KER 5 feature four complementary commercial streams that generate revenue, all of which rely on the provision of expert human capital and knowledge services. The major source of revenue comes from consulting fees, which are charged on an hourly basis or project basis for the implementation or advisory services rendered. The fees generated from training programmes for corporate training cohorts and structured capability development programmes provide a significant scaled income opportunity that grows as the demand for DATAMITE expertise increases in European industry. Ongoing support contracts provide predictable repeat revenue for customers needing ongoing technical assistance and maintenance advice on DATAMITE installations. The fees for certification are imposed on the individuals and organizations that take part in the Tech Expert and the Tech Trainer programs. This serves as an extra layer of income as well as strengthen the expert network's supply side.

3.9. Revenue Stream Models

DATAMITE's revenue model is deliberately multi-layered, combining open-source community reach with commercial monetisation paths, designed to generate value for the full spectrum of consortium partners — from RTOs and universities pursuing research income to technology companies and SMEs pursuing direct commercial returns. The project formally identifies three primary revenue-generating streams, each anchored to a different exploitation model:

Stream 1 – Subscription and Licensing Fees

The foundational commercial revenue stream centres on **subscription fees for integrating the DATAMITE cognitive layer**, covering operating licence and maintenance costs for organisations deploying the framework. This model targets organisations that require ongoing access to the full suite of modules — Data Governance (DGM), Data Quality (DQM), Data Security (DSEM), and Data Sharing and Trading (DSTM) — along with integration support and platform maintenance.

Six distinct pricing model types are recognised for data-related transactions relevant to DATAMITE's offering: **free of charge, fixed-price, subscription or flat-rate, pay-per-use, progressive, and auction-based**. The framework is specifically designed to address the market's rejection of disproportionately high licensing costs associated with proprietary platforms such as SAP, Siemens MindSphere, Atos Codex, and Capgemini Invent, which impose steep learning curves and are accessible mainly to large enterprises. DATAMITE's open-source core

eliminates this barrier while leaving commercial licensing space for advanced components (Data Support tools) developed beyond the open-source baseline, for which a commercial licensing plan is generated early in the project lifecycle.

Target adopters: Large Enterprises, medium-sized companies, DSOs, telecom operators, and corporate conglomerates seeking to deploy DATAMITE modules within their own infrastructure.

Stream 2 – Commercial Agreements with Third-Party Module Developers and Integrators

The second major revenue stream stems from **commercial business agreements with third-party device suppliers and module developers/integrators** to certify and integrate their assets with the DATAMITE framework, including monetised access to datasets through APIs. This stream is operationalised through the **DATAMITE Advanced Components KER**, where advanced modules — including anonymisation algorithms, bias detection tools, access control mechanisms, and privacy preservation tools — are individually commercialised and targeted to specific user needs and industry domains.

Partner	Commercial Role
ITI	Framework integrator; API licensing; DIH-mediated SME onboarding
CERTH	Visual analytics and anomaly detection tools; consulting for data space integration
TEC	Brokers and plugins for the IDS/Gaia-X ecosystem; integration services
LOBA	Professional frontend development and UX services for DATAMITE deployments
ICCS	Ontology alignment and semantic interoperability tool commercialisation
FHG	Quality assurance, security risk analysis, and Data Spaces Support Centre coordination
1001LAKES	Data monetisation strategy blueprints; action blueprints for business model design

Table 5. Partners' Commercial Role

The DATAMITE ecosystem also enables **DIHs** (Digital Innovation Hubs) to enrich their product and service portfolio, with ITI's EUH4D network of 20+ EU DIHs serving as a primary multiplier channel; the consortium's KPI targets 20 EU DIHs engaged in the community.

- **Stream 3 – Training, Certification and Consulting Services**

The third revenue stream derives from **training and certification materials, facilitating digital upskilling**—both through the direct sale of premium training packages and by positioning consortium members as certified **DATAMITE Tech Experts and Tech Trainers**. This stream is formalised under the **KER#3 – Monetisation Strategies** and the **KER#5 — Tech Experts and Training Services**.

The consulting revenue model is structured as follows:

- **Open-access training materials** (Documentation, reports & MooC-based modules): Free publication to attract the business user base and upskill personnel; serves as a market entry channel.
- **Certified Tech Expert services:** Consortium partners labelled as DATAMITE Tech Experts provide personalised assessments to satisfy corporate needs or specific training demands; customers pay for tailored consultancy.
- **Certified Tech Trainer pipeline:** Partners become certified Tech Trainers who, in turn, certify new Experts, creating a scalable, self-perpetuating revenue model beyond the project's lifetime.
- **Consulting for data monetisation strategy adoption:** Led by FIR (business model strategies), UCC (KPI catalogue for dataset valuation), and 1001LAKES (action blueprints); provided as fee-based advisory services to EU companies seeking to implement data monetisation strategies.
- **Legal and ethical compliance consulting:** LIF, ZSI and UCC provide fee-based legal advisory on data transfers, trading compliance under GDPR, the Data Governance Act, and the Data Act.

Market Context for Revenue Projections

DATAMITE serves a fast-growing market. The global data monetisation market reached a value of ~€3 billion in 2023 and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 16.6% through 2032, thereby attaining a value of ~€10 billion by 2028. The data economy in the European Union reached €829 billion in 2020 (5.6% of EU GDP), whereas the data spaces in Europe are anticipated to add another €500 billion to its GDP by 2025. Therefore, this shows that there is a substantial demand for DATAMITE tools which are open source and cover important issues regarding quality, interoperability and skills gap. This growing demand is driven by the increasing transparency prevalent in the

European data economy. More information and market analysis are already provided in the first exploitation report [D6.4 \(M18\)](#).

Revenue Stream	Partners	Exploitation Model
Subscription & licensing fees	ITI, CERTH, TEC, LOBA	Commercial
Module integration agreements & API access	ITI, TEC, ICCS, FHG	Commercial / Technological
Business model consulting & strategy advisory	FIR, 1001LAKES, UCC, OTE	Commercial
Legal & ethical compliance advisory	LIF, ZSI, UCC	Commercial
Open access training materials	ITI, PSNC, UCC, CERTH	Open-source / Research
Certified Tech Expert/Trainer services	All technology partners	Commercial
DIH-mediated SME onboarding	ITI (EUH4D network)	Commercial / Technological
Follow-on R&D grants	ALL	Research

Table 6. Revenue Streams & Exploitation Models

3.10. Commercialization Roadmap

Phase 1 – Foundation and Market Intelligence (M1–M18)

The first Reporting Period (RP1: M1–M18) established all analytical and strategic foundations necessary for effective commercialisation, as formally tracked via Milestone 4 (Business and outreach activity report) and reported in D6.4 (Impact Assessment, Exploitation & Standards Report M18)

- **Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identification:** Through a dedicated Value Proposition Canvas workshop (M12), the consortium identified three KERs:
 - Business Model Strategies
 - Open-Source Core FRAMEWORK
 - DATA Support tools
 - Consulting & Training Resources

and assessed associated background/foreground IP in accordance with Grant Agreement Article 16.4 and Annex 5.

- **Market analysis and positioning:** The global data monetisation market was valued at approximately €3 billion in 2023 and is projected to reach €10 billion by 2028 at a CAGR of 16.6%; the EU data market itself is expected to grow from ~€90 billion (2025) to ~€125 billion (2030)

Phase 2 – Development and Pilot Validation (M19–M39)

The second Reporting Period (RP2: M19–M39) encompassed full pilot deployment and business model development per KER. Key exploitation deliverables produced in this phase include:

- Strategies for Improving Data Monetisation
- KPI Catalogue for Dataset Valuation
- Action Blueprints for Business Model Design
- Value of Data Sharing on SSH
- Legal & Ethical Guidelines
- LLM-based RAG System for Data Monetisation Strategies
- Pilot Demonstrators
- **Three exploitation models per KER:** Commercial (paid licensing), Technological (integration into new products/services), and Research (use of know-how in future projects); selection guided by partner profile and KER nature.
- **Pilot-based TRL elevation:** Six pilots across agriculture (WODR), energy (HEDNO, E-REDES), multi-domain corporate exchange (GIDI), telecommunications (OTE), and climate research (CINECA) validated the framework at **TRL 7** by M39.

Phase 3 – Go-to-Market (M33–M39)

In September 2025, DATAMITE engaged the Horizon Results Booster Entry Level Consultation (ELC) service. The ELC, conducted across two calls on 22 and 30 September 2025, with participation from AUS, ITI and Booster mentors, confirmed all D&E building blocks were in place. Beyond March 2026, DATAMITE's commercialisation is sustained through three formally identified channels:

- **Open-source community:** Eclipse Foundation governance ensures the framework remains actively maintained; the Eclipse Marketplace and EOSC Marketplace serve as primary deployment platforms.

- **Commercial and consulting services:** Technology provider partners (ITI, CERTH, TEC, LOBA, 1001LAKES, FIR) will offer integration, advisory, and training services, generating revenue while expanding the user base into EU SMEs and DIHs.
- **Follow-on funding:** Identified pathways include EIC Transition (up to €2.5M), EIC Accelerator (up to €15M equity), Eurostars, Digital Europe Programme, Cascading Grants, InvestEU, and the Enterprise Europe Network.

3.11. Early Adopter Commitments

Partner	Pilot	Commitment
GIDI	Pilot 1 – Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with DIH Support	Integration into production data architecture; continued Docker-based deployment
OTE	Pilot 2 – Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange	Production evaluation of Trino cross-database queries; stress-tested with 200M+ records
HEDNO	Pilot 3 – Offering Data to Service Providers with DataSpaces	Integration into energy data sharing workflows; access/usage policy deployment via EDC
E-REDES	Pilot 4 – Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data	Ongoing publication of open data to the Opendatasoft portal; data product lifecycle management
WODR/AGREGO	Pilot 5 – Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets	Publication of agricultural data products to the Pontus-X marketplace; weather data governance
CINECA	Pilot 6 – Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AI-ON-Demand Platform	Continued dissemination of climate datasets to the EU AIoD platform; quality tagging via UDRG

Table 7. Pilot Partner Commitments

3.12. Replication Opportunities

The DATAMITE pilot validation confirms strong replication potential across four strategic sectors:

Agriculture: The eDWIN pilot (WODR/AGREGO) validated the Agriculture Information Model (AIM) for plant protection and weather data governance. The framework is directly replicable for other national agricultural advisory agencies and farm management system providers across the EU, particularly within the CAP digital transformation agenda.

Energy: Pilots 3 and 4 (HEDNO, E-REDES) demonstrated the creation of data products, GDPR-compliant anonymisation, and open data publication for electricity distribution. Replication is

feasible across European DSOs (Distribution System Operators) operating under the EU Energy Data Space framework.

Telecommunications: Pilot 2 (OTE) validated cross-database interoperability across MongoDB, MariaDB, and PostgreSQL at scale. The solution is directly replicable for other telecom operators managing heterogeneous data infrastructures.

Research & Climate Data: Pilot 6 (CINECA/MISTRAL) demonstrated integration with the EU AloD platform and quality assessment of observational sensor data. Replication is identified for other research data infrastructure providers and meteorological institutes within the EOSC ecosystem.

4. Standardisation Activities

Building on the standardisation work started in D6.4, and with DIN coordinating T6.3, the focus in M19–M39 shifted from listing topics and gaps to making the first concrete contributions Standardization Strategy.

4.1. Standardisation Potentials Workshop

Purpose and concept

The standardisation potentials workshop was conducted in M19. It was already briefly mentioned in Clause 7.4 of Deliverable D6.4 that a standardisation potential workshop was being prepared. The goal of this workshop was to identify potential topics for the development of new standards, drawing on the practical experiences, daily tasks, and challenges faced by the project partners. Additionally, the workshop sought to create a shared and coordinated strategy for advancing standardisation activities, leveraging the collective expertise of all participants involved in the DATAMITE project. Since the Horizon Calls focus on emerging and significant topics in new fields, it was likely that the project partners would encounter the need for either new standards or the adaptation of existing ones during the course of their work. This workshop concept has been successfully applied in previous Horizon projects, such as DiMAT and has been specifically tailored to meet the requirements of DATAMITE.

Standards are intended to serve as fundamental enablers, providing a shared framework upon which innovations in emerging technologies can be built. However, in certain cases, disruptive technologies may not be fully supported by existing standards, necessitating revisions or updates. To address this, one of the key activities undertaken was the standardisation potentials workshop. The agenda for this workshop is presented in Table 1.

Description	Contributors
1. Welcome & Introduction	DIN
2. Familiarization with „Conceptboard“ (interactive)	all
3. Basics on standardisation (interactive)	all
Break	all
Group Photo	all
4. „Back to the future“ – What does a successful project look like?	DIN
5. Relevant technical committees for possible contribution (interactive)	all

6. Standardisation potentials <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Identification of challenges & identification of potentials (interactive) ○ Presentation of ideas (DIN) ○ Rating of ideas (interactive) 	all
7. Outlook and next steps	DIN
Feedback	all

Table 8. Standardisation Potentials Workshop Agenda

Results

During the working phase of the workshop, relevant technical committees at the international and European levels were presented, based on the standards research outlined in Clause 5.3 of Deliverable D6.4. Most of the participants expressed interest in the CEN/CLC Focus Group „Data, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge“ as this could be relevant for DATAMITE with regard to a collaboration to possibly contribute to ongoing standardisation activities. At the time of the workshop, this was still a focus group with no tangible standardisation deliverable, but was converted into CEN/CLC/JTC 25 “Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud, and Edge” afterwards in September 2024.

Furthermore, during the workshop phase, a total of 20 ideas were developed and briefly presented afterwards. The results are displayed on the board in Figure 1.

Figure 10. Standardisation Workshop Brainstorming Board

The results were grouped and voted to see where the participants see their priority. The results of the top ideas are further detailed in Table 2, which only includes ideas that received two or more votes.

Topic	Standard Type	Description	Score
Data Spaces	Trust Common requirements	Data monetization strategies could support others, but how to standardise it when each company entity has their own requirements?	5
Data Quality	Common language	Extension to DQV "W3C Recommendation" to be able to specify User defined rules for creating new Custom Metrics for measuring the quality of the datasets.	3
Data Quality	Others	Data Quality Dimensions and Categories Data dimensions and categories are contemplated as a relevant property in DQV. Apparently, there is no clear definition or standardisation on what these dimensions or categories should be, what impacts the semantic interoperability from the data quality point of view, as users may be using different categories or dimensions to refer to the same concepts.	2
Others	Others	Standardized maturity model monetization strategies from T4.3	2

Table 9. Standardisation Voting Results

4.2. CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) Development Progress

Two of the mentioned ideas in Figure 1 deal with monetization strategies. Therefore, these two ideas were forged into one idea. A total of four calls were scheduled to discuss the three ideas and further refine them in collaboration with the idea providers and other interested stakeholders. In these calls, it became clear to the participants that the topic of data monetization strategies is difficult to transfer into a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). Afterwards a final ballot was conducted to determine, which one of the following topics should be transferred into a CWA:

- Extension to Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV) "W3C Recommendation"
 - o To be able to specify user defined rules for creating new custom metrics for measuring the quality of the datasets.
- Data Quality Dimensions and Categories

o Data dimensions and categories are contemplated as a relevant property in DQV. Apparently, there is no clear definition or standardisation on what these dimensions or categories should be, what impacts the semantic interoperability from the data quality point of view, as users may be using different categories or dimensions to refer to the same concepts.

The DATAMITE consortium saw more potential in the extension to DQV "W3C Recommendation". While making preparations for a CWA proposal, the proposer of the standardisation idea doubted whether it would be the appropriate route to develop a CWA, while the topic itself deals with an existing W3C Recommendation. Therefore, discussions were held with W3C members to receive guidance. In these discussions it became clear that developing a W3C Recommendation takes time and needs support by the W3C community, as a dedicated W3C Working Group first has to be established. W3C Working Groups are only created if there is enough interest among W3C members, or the wider community at large, to develop a given specification. Also, W3C Working Groups do not start specifications from scratch, as they adopt specifications that have been incubated, typically in W3C Community Groups. These Community Groups develop "Community Group reports", that can be published on the w3.org website, but are explicitly not endorsed by W3C nor its members. Some of them are then adopted by a Working Group and turned into W3C Recommendations. But there are also examples of Community Group reports that have had large adoption without even moving to that stage. Therefore, DATAMITE decided to not develop a W3C Recommendation, as there were doubts whether the envisaged standardisation deliverable would even be endorsed by W3C. Besides, the W3C member explained that the intended extension of the W3C DQV "Recommendation" is not considered a "W3C Recommendation", but a "W3C Note", meaning that it is not a normative document. Extending a standardisation deliverable by developing a CWA not containing any normative requirements is not feasible, as CWAs shall contain requirements. Therefore, developing a CWA was not compelling anymore for DATAMITE and there was not enough support to develop a CWA for the topic of "Data Quality Dimensions and Categories".

4.3. Technical Committee Engagement

As mentioned in Deliverable D6.1 in Section 5.3 and 5.4, the possibility remained to contribute to ongoing standardization activities. During the standardisation potentials workshop while addressing International and European technical committees, the participants expressed the most interests in the CEN/CLC Focus Group „Data, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge“. While the standardisation potentials workshop took place in M19, this focus group was still only a focus

group with no standardisation deliverables. After realizing that it is not suitable for DATAMITE to develop its own standardisation deliverable, the CEN/CLC focus group was already converted to the European Joint Technical Committee CEN/CLC/JTC 25 “Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud, and Edge” with its own work items. In M31, the JTC 25 leadership consisting of the Chair and Secretary was contacted to schedule a meeting with DATAMITE to explore whether a liaison between DATAMITE and JTC 25 makes sense. In this call, the following standardisation deliverables were identified to be relevant for DATAMITE:

WI number	Title
JT025001	Implementation framework for data catalogue (DCAT) profiles and extensions.
JT025003	Maturity assessment of Common European Data Spaces
JT025004	Quality assessment of internal data governance processes

Table 10. Standardisation Deliverables (WI)

Following the meeting with the JTC 25 leadership, preparations for developing the liaison request were made. The liaison request was submitted to CEN/CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) in M33. To decide whether a liaison is granted, the technical committee creates a Committee Internal Ballot (CIB), which takes four weeks. This ballot ended on October 31st, 2025, and was approved. Afterwards, CCMC sent a liaison agreement to DATAMITE, which needed to be examined by the legal department of the project coordinator of ITI. The liaison agreement was signed in M39. As the appointed observer on behalf of DATAMITE intends to still be part of JTC 25 after the project DATAMITE ends, DATAMITE decided that a liaison would still make sense bringing in DATAMITE results to possibly contribute to JTC 25 work items.

4.4. CEN-CLC/JTC 25 – Data management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge

The following section gives brief background information on the work carried out by CEN-CLC/JTC 25.

The development and coordination of standards are essential to support the implementation of data sharing and processing concepts, guidelines, mechanisms, and their ecosystems. Current standards, along with ongoing international standardization projects, highlight the importance of integrating ISO, IEC, or ISO/IEC standards while also identifying the need for new standards, especially those that align closely with EU policies. To address this, CEN and CENELEC created

the Joint Technical Committee 25 (CEN-CLC/JTC 25) on Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud, and Edge. This committee is responsible for establishing a comprehensive standardization framework and responding to future standardization requests from the European Commission. Promoting collaboration with existing European Technical Committees (TCs) and Sub-committees (SCs) is also a central priority.

Since its founding on 20 September 2024, JTC 25 has brought together over 127 experts from 26 countries. These experts collaborate across four dedicated Working Groups (WGs) to achieve the committee's goals.

CEN/CLC JTC 25 develops deliverables for Data Management, Dataspaces, Cloud and Edge in conjunction with the European Trusted Data Framework, based on but not limited to standards on:

- Data governance, including data quality and lifecycle management
- Interoperability, as well as portability and switchability
- Organizational frameworks and methodologies
- Evaluation schemes for assessing processes and products
- Smart technologies and systems, including smart objects, distributed computing devices, and data services

Sector-specific standards are excluded and will be developed in the respective technical committees covering the sectors. Further exclusions include deliverables already covered by the scope of other CEN and CENELEC TCs and the definition of the content of data belonging to different product types or segments.

CEN-CLC/JTC 25 operates through a plenary committee and four dedicated working groups (WGs):

Working Group	Title
CEN/CLC/JTC 25/WG 1	Advisory group
CEN/CLC/JTC 25/WG 2	Dataspaces
CEN/CLC/JTC 25/WG 3	Data management and governance
CEN/CLC/JTC 25/WG 4	Cloud & Edge

Table 11. JTC 25 Working Groups

The current work programme of CEN/CLC/JTC 25 can be found in the Table 4 and also on the [CEN/CENELEC website](#):

Project reference	Status	Initial Date	Current Stage	Next Stage	Forecast ed voting date
EN 18235-1:2026 (WI=JT025009) Trusted data transactions - Part 1: Terminology, concepts and mechanisms	Approved	2025-05-25	2026-02-23	2026-03-25	2025-11-17
FprCEN/CLC/TS 18331 (WI=JT025010) Maturity assessment of Common European Data Spaces	Under Approval	2025-08-18	2026-01-15	2026-04-09	
prCEN/TS XXX (WI=JT025015) Requirements for Implementation tools and artefacts for data governance, data management and data quality supporting trusted data sharing	Under Drafting	2026-02-18	2026-02-18		
prCEN/TS XXX (WI=JT025006) Cloud Computing - Switching and Interoperability in a European context	Under Drafting	2025-06-16	2025-06-16	2025-12-16	
prEN 18235-2 (WI=JT025008) Trusted data transactions - Part 2: Trustworthiness requirements	Under Approval	2025-05-17	2026-03-05	2026-05-02	2026-05-02
prEN 18235-3 (WI=JT025007) Trusted Data Transactions - Part 3: Interoperability requirements.	Under Drafting	2025-06-11	2025-06-11		2026-10-13
prEN 18352 (WI=JT025011) Quality framework for internal data governance for participants in data spaces	Under Enquiry	2025-08-20	2026-03-05	2026-05-28	2026-11-09
prEN ISO/IEC 22123-1 (WI=JT025012) Information technology - Cloud computing - Part 1: Vocabulary (ISO/IEC 22123-1:2023)	Under Approval	2025-09-25	2026-03-05	2027-04-30	2027-04-30
prEN ISO/IEC 22123-2 (WI=JT025013) Information technology - Cloud computing - Part 2: Concepts (ISO/IEC 22123-2:2023)	Under Approval	2025-09-25	2026-03-05	2027-06-27	2027-06-27
prEN ISO/IEC 22123-3 (WI=JT025014) Information technology - Cloud computing - Part 3: Reference architecture (ISO/IEC 22123-3:2023)	Under Approval	2025-09-25	2026-03-05	2027-06-27	2027-06-27
(WI=JT025016) Overview and architecture of standards in support of the European Trusted Data Framework	Preliminary		2026-03-09		
(WI=JT025017) Trust frameworks for data spaces - European specific context and approach	Preliminary		2026-03-09		2027-12-17
(WI=JT025018) Data quality in data spaces	Preliminary		2026-03-09		2027-12-17

Table 12. CEN/CLC/JTC 25 Current Work Programme

Conclusions

The DATAMITE project for Europe’s data monetisation is a three-year project that at its conclusion will leave behind a mature and pilot-validated open-source framework. The five Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of the project—reference architecture, core modules, business plans, support tools, and training services—managed to achieve TRL 7 through six industrial piloting in agriculture, energy, telecommunications and meteorology, resulting in improved quality, governance, security and sharing of data. This significant level of technical maturation and the comprehensive planning of exploitation makes DATAMITE a key contributor to the EU’s data economy objectives under the Data Act, Data Governance Act and Common European Data Spaces.

The open-source core framework and its DGM, DQM, DSEM, DSM, and DSTM modules proved to be robust enough to be applied successfully in real-world environments. It affords the data management process a FAIR compliance while at the same time guaranteeing sovereignty leveraging IDS/Gaia-X. The seamless publication of data products was achieved through the EDC extensions and the pilots’ validation of interoperability with ecosystems such as EOSC, Pontus-X, and AI-on-Demand. Tools to address various sectoral needs, e.g. UDRG; anonymisation pipelines; harmonisation using Trino, have contributed to a reduction of friction for SMEs, DIHs. The architecture reference, and the monetisation blueprints of KER 3 provided blueprints ready for deployment, while KER 5 provided 16+ training modules (Moodle courses, webinars, videos), which reached through “Training Pills” training of 200+ users.

Research, training, standardisation, commercialisation and policy are the five exploitation pathways which offer a clear post-M39 continuity. The revenue models which include open-source stewardship with EPL/MIT licensing through Eclipse, consulting and training, support tools, and feeing for integration into existing ecosystems are targeting the contribution to Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) SMEs and the public sector adopters. Each KER has a business model canvas depicting hybrid streams around subscription for support, white-label customisations. Gaps in DQV extensions, data quality dimensions and monetisation maturity models have been identified and prioritised based on voting in workshops. The CEN work item that DIN coordinates aims at a CEN workshop agreement (CWA) that defines metrics for the user defined quality verification (DQV) and a JTC 25 data governance work item. The target groups are CEN, CLC and JTC 25. Patterns from the pilots are fed into IDSA/BDVA to ensure the sustainability of DATAMITE in European data spaces.

The success of DATAMITE lies in multi-domain validation, open sourcing (26 partners, 12 countries), and pragmatic phasing. The takeaways were: (1) pilots show interoperability is more important than perfection; (2) skills gap requires hybrid technology/business training; (3) sovereignty drives adoption on features; (4) layered monetisation (open core + services) preserves accessibility and sustainability. Using a modular design along with compliance-first architecture, legacy integration as well as regulatory flux challenges were mitigated.